

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 2023 Annual Report

Volume 2

Non-focal Project Results

Vernal pool at Weisberger-Pohlman Nature Preserve Restoration, July 7, 2023.

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Note: The data and management summaries contained in this report are provisional. Every effort has been made to ensure their correctness. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is supported by the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, the US Environmental Protection Agency's Great Lake Restoration Initiative, and the Ohio Water Development Authority. The information, findings, and conclusions in this article are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the funding organizations. Any use of trade, product, or firm names is for descriptive purposes only and does not imply endorsement by the State of Ohio or U.S. Government. Contact the ODNR'S H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program prior to using these data and before citing research and management findings.

Non-focal Project Results

The following sections describe the Project Overview, Nutrient Load Reduction Assessment, Management Considerations, Sampling Approach, and Monitoring Considerations for each Non-focal Project routinely monitored by the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program from 2021 to 2023. In each Non-focal Project section, Sampling Location Water Depths, Surface Water Concentrations, and Soil Nutrient Status results are preliminarily summarized (i.e., values aggregated across sampling locations and season and briefly interpreted by researchers). Unless otherwise noted, all surface water and soil results are presented as mean \pm standard deviation.

In addition to the tables and figures contained in this document, supplemental data are presented in an accompanying **H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program: 2023 Annual Progress Report Appendices** (A–C) document. External appendix figures include letters to represent A) Focal Projects Appendix, B) Non-Focal Projects Appendix, and C) Vegetation Data Appendix. Some elements within this document may be repeated in the Appendix.

Note: The data and management summaries contained in this report are provisional. Every effort has been made to ensure their correctness. The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is supported by the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, the US Environmental Protection Agency’s Great Lake Restoration Initiative, and the Ohio Water Development Authority. The information, findings, and conclusions in this article are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the funding organizations. Any use of trade, product, or firm names is for descriptive purposes only and does not imply endorsement by the State of Ohio or U.S. Government. Contact the ODNR’S H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program prior to using these data and before citing research and management findings.

Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection (DARR)

Project Overview

Ottawa County | La Carpe Creek Watershed | Coastal

Project Size: 352.2 Acres

Partners: Ottawa Soil & Water Conservation District, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service

ODNR Description: “Two wetland units in Darby Refuge were reconnected to Lake Erie in August 2021. The reconnection will increase the amount of excess nutrients and sediment captured in the watershed before they are able to flow into the lake. The project will include breaching existing structures/levees and installing water control structures to allow La Carpe Creek to flow through the wetlands instead of emptying agricultural drainage into Lake Erie directly.”¹

Management Considerations

Accurate information about wetland water levels and connectivity between wetland units and adjacent waterways is critical to elucidate wetland nutrient retention, particularly in coastal wetland reconnection projects like the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project (hereafter Darby Project). Accurate and prompt reporting of water level management actions (e.g., via Survey123 or email) between LaCarpe Creek and Pools 1 and 4 in the Darby Project will allow researchers to generate actionable data to inform management actions and derive better estimates of nutrient retention. Monitoring Program researchers will continue to engage with wetland managers to develop effective methods to share information about water level management actions. Additional management considerations include construction constraints on Project property, which can substantially alter the hydrology of the Project. For example, in 2023 the ditch connecting LaCarpe Creek and the wetland parcels was completely drained for a construction project involving water level management structures at the Darby Project.

Sampling Approach

Hydrologically, the Darby Project consists of two wetland parcels (Pool 1 and Pool 4) and LaCarpe Creek. The parcels are permanently inundated, open-water wetlands surrounded by dike roads (Figure 1.1). These parcels are hydrologically isolated from LaCarpe Creek and Lake Erie except for the three water control structures (WCS) in the ditch connected to LaCarpe Creek (WCS 1–3; Figure 1.1). The sampling approach at the Darby Project is designed to investigate and compare surface water and soil nutrient concentrations across these wetland parcels, LaCarpe Creek, and the adjoining ditch.

There are nine sampling locations shown in Figure 1.1 and Table B1.1 that are grouped into two categories: within wetland pools (hereafter Wetland, or Pool 1 and Pool 4) and outside of wetland pools (hereafter Creek/Ditch). There are five sampling locations situated in the Wetland:

¹ “Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/darby-refuge-wetland-reconnection/>

three sampling locations in Pool 1 (Pool 1 WCS, Pool 1 Center, and Pool 1 WCS2), and two in Pool 4 (Pool 4 WCS3 and Pool 4 Center). Samples collected from Pool 1 Center and Pool 4 Center serve to assess open-water nutrient concentrations within the wetland parcels, while Pool 1 WCS1, Pool 1 WCS2, and Pool 4 WCS3 samples are collected to investigate nutrient concentrations near the water control structures. LaCarpe Creek and its ditch contain four sampling locations: Creek Outlet, Creek WCS1, Ditch WCS2, and Ditch WCS3. Samples collected at these locations comprise nutrient-rich surface runoff from the surrounding agricultural land use.

Figure 1.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Water depths throughout the Wetland (Pool 1 WCS, Pool 1 Center, Pool 1 WCS2, Pool 4 WCS3 and Pool 4 Center) and Creek/Ditch (Creek Outlet, Creek WCS1, Ditch WCS2, and Ditch WCS3) were similar and around 25–40 cm (Table B1.2). Omitting Pool 4 Center due to a limited

sample size ($n=1$), Ditch WCS2 had the greatest mean depth (40 ± 12 cm), yet Pool 1 WCS1 had the greatest maximum depth (104 cm; Figure 1.2).

It is important to note that water depth interpretations should be taken with slight caution because variation in the bottom substrate may have influenced the precision of measurements. For example, sampling locations near the water control structures are characterized by a rocky, uneven substrate and microtopography that made manual water depth measurements fallible in 2023 given the challenge to determine the position of the water-sediment interface. However, the magnitude of potential inaccuracies does not preclude preliminary interpretation of observed patterns.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Pool 1 WCS2 and Ditch WCS3 had the greatest mean dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) concentrations (0.055 ± 0.1 and 0.048 ± 0.1 mg P/L, respectively; $n > 10$) while Pool 4 Center had the lowest (0.004 ± 0 mg P/L, $n = 3$; Table B1.4). Interestingly, DRP and TP concentrations in the Creek Outlet and in the Creek at the last water control structure along the flow path before the outlet (Creek WCS1) were lower on average (DRP = 0.008 ± 0 , $n = 13$ and 0.009 ± 0 , TP = 0.064 ± 0 and 0.085 ± 0 mg P/L, respectively; $n > 12$) than other sampling locations within the Wetland (e.g., Pool 1; Table B1.4). However, sampling locations near water control structures had consistently higher average DRP and TP concentrations than those in the center of wetland pools, highlighting the different hydrologic exchange in different areas of the Wetland. Fall had the greatest maximum DRP concentration observed, but winter had the highest DRP concentration on average (Table B1.5). Summer had the highest mean TP concentrations (Table B1.5), while June 2022 and September 2023 had the most variable DRP and TP concentrations among sampling locations in the Darby Project (Figure 1.3).

Creek Outlet and Creek WCS1 had the greatest mean nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) concentrations (0.458 ± 0.6 and 0.383 ± 0.4 mg N/L, respectively) whereas Pool 1 WCS1 and Pool 1 WCS2 had the lowest (0.04 ± 0 and 0.037 ± 0 mg N/L, respectively; Table 1.1). Creek Outlet had the highest average total ammonia (NH₃; 0.097 ± 0.1 mg N/L), but other locations had higher maximum values, such as Ditch WCS2 (0.628 mg N/L; Table 1.1). Mean total nitrogen (TN) concentrations were similar among sites, yet Pool 4 WCS3 and Ditch WCS3 had the greatest maximum values (3.621 and 2.688 mg N/L, respectively; Table 1.1). Spring exhibited the greatest mean NO_x concentrations (0.274 ± 0.5 mg N/L). Surface water TN was elevated in the spring and summer compared to fall (Table B1.7).

Non-Focal Projects: Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection (DARR)

Figure 1.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Non-Focal Projects: Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection (DARR)

Figure 1.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table 1.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Creek Outlet	0.458 ± 0.6	13 (0)	0.03–2.2	0.097 ± 0.1	13 (0)	0.01–0.26	1.012 ± 0.5	13 (0)	0.3–2.09
02. Pool 1 WCS1	0.04 ± 0	16 (0)	0–0.09	0.046 ± 0	16 (0)	0.02–0.1	1.124 ± 0.5	16 (0)	0.42–1.85
03. Creek WCS1	0.383 ± 0.4	14 (0)	0.01–1.58	0.079 ± 0	14 (0)	0–0.13	1.146 ± 0.4	14 (0)	0.57–2.01
04. Pool 1 Center	0.056 ± 0	3 (0)	0–0.1	0.029 ± 0	3 (0)	0.02–0.04	1.365 ± 0.3	3 (0)	1.04–1.71
05. Pool 1 WCS2	0.037 ± 0	14 (0)	0–0.1	0.072 ± 0.1	14 (1)	0–0.46	0.932 ± 0.3	14 (0)	0.48–1.27
06. Ditch WCS2	0.056 ± 0.1	12 (0)	0–0.26	0.085 ± 0.2	12 (0)	0.02–0.63	0.936 ± 0.4	12 (0)	0.4–2.04
07. Pool 4 WCS3	0.051 ± 0.1	17 (0)	0–0.31	0.039 ± 0	17 (0)	0.02–0.11	1.182 ± 0.9	17 (0)	0–3.62
08. Ditch WCS3	0.048 ± 0.1	14 (0)	0–0.22	0.047 ± 0.1	14 (1)	0–0.24	1.318 ± 0.6	14 (0)	0.52–2.69
09. Pool 4 Center	0.033 ± 0	3 (0)	0–0.05	0.019 ± 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.02	0.747 ± 0.1	3 (0)	0.65–0.83

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil pH was similar among all sampling locations, and slightly alkaline (i.e., pH > 7) on average (Table B1.8). Pool 1 WCS2 showed the greatest range in soil pH values (6.7–7.8). Mean soil conductivity was the greatest and most variable at Pool 1 WCS1 (Table B1.8). Except for Pool 1 WCS2, low concentrations of Mehlich 3-extracted aluminum (M3-Al) and iron (M3-Fe) in the soil resulted in positive but modest Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC; Table B1.10). Pool 1 WCS2 had the greatest mean concentration of M3-Fe leading to an above average SPSC (70.25 ± 92.6 mg P/kg). Yet, SPSC calculated at Pool 1 WCS2 showed great variability, ranging between 12–208 mg P/kg (Table B1.10). Overall, due to low Fe and Al concentrations in the soil (i.e., M3-Fe and M3-Al), there appears to be preliminary evidence of low SPSC at this Project (Figure 1.4).

Figure 1.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Darby Refuge Wetland Reconnection project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range

of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

Central sampling locations show nutrient retention potential (Table 1.1), but they are the most difficult to access due to dense vegetation and safety concerns.

Nutrient Load Calculation

Nutrient load reduction estimates were not possible for the Darby Project in 2023 because of lack of reliable water depth/level data. Installation of staff gauges to accurately measure water level will allow estimation of volume changes in the wetland units. Information about water control structure management actions in the Darby Project will be necessary for nutrient load calculations.

Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve (FRUW)

Project Overview

Seneca County | Sandusky River Watershed

Project size: 18 Acres

Partners: Seneca County Park District

ODNR Description: “The Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve is located in Seneca County near Wolf Creek just to the East of Fostoria. This is a depressional isolated wetland that primarily collects only rainwater and is an area where the groundwater table is high enough to sustain pools almost year-round. The project used to be a soccer field that was frequently flooded prior to being converted into a wetland. The project is located at the boundary of two different subwatersheds to Wolf Creek. The west side of the project (not wooded) ultimately connects to Wolf Creek to the southeast via shallow groundwater. The east side, which is entirely wooded, flows through a swale towards Emerson Ditch, but moves to subsurface flow in the tiled section of the nearby agricultural field prior to reaching the ditch.”²

Management Considerations

The Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve restoration was successful overall. Prior to restoration, this area of land was consistently wet even with installed subsurface tile drainage. Conversion to the wetland greatly increased water storage on-site, which ultimately contributes to reduced peak streamflows downstream. That said, without direct surface or tile drain inflow to the wetland, the expected nutrient load reductions are limited due to the low nutrient concentrations in the surface water of the pools. Future projects similar to this one should consider how to receive runoff from nearby areas to increase nutrient processing.

Sampling Approach

Because the project is a depressional isolated wetland, the main events that influence the hydrology are seasonal variation in the groundwater table and precipitation. There are four pools in the western portion of the project (Figure 2.1; Table B2.1). Pool 1 is a collection of deep pools with a small surface area that connect into one large pool when the water table is high, hence there are multiple sub-pools (A-D). Pools 3 and 4 are within a bermed area of the project that also contains microtopography with small hummocks and hollows. Pool 2 was invaded by cattail in 2023 and was dredged towards the end of the summer. The eastern portion of the project has a vernal pool and swale, which has never been observed to contain water. There are no adjacent streams or ditches to serve as inlets or outlets for the site.

Our sampling goal is to characterize the seasonal variation in water quality in each pool as the water table fluctuates and to capture periods of time when the potential for phosphorus release is highest (high water temperature, low dissolved oxygen). For this Project, it is especially

² “Fruth Outdoor Center Wetland Restoration.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/fruth-outdoor-center-wetland-restoration/>

important to quantify variation in water level to be able to assess the water volume stored in the project area. Therefore, we have continuous water level monitoring sensors in each major pool. Groundwater monitoring wells have also been installed (2022) and will be monitored in the future to assess the nutrient concentrations in the subsurface water.

Figure 2.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Water depth varied by sampling location and season (Tables B2.2 and B2.3; Figure 2.2). While the deepest pools were in the Pond 1 complex, they tended to dry each summer and fall and have far fewer measurements. Ponds 2, 3, and 4 consistently had more water and were similar in depth on average (24–33 cm). We only observed water in the vernal pool once and have not observed water in the swale. Across seasons, water was deepest in the winter and spring (average 26–38 cm) compared to summer and fall (average 21–26 cm; Table B2.3).

Figure 2.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Across all of the sampling locations, dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) was fairly low (< 0.05 mg P/L) compared to the nearby Sandusky River which averages ~0.1 mg P/L annually. That said, DRP was slightly higher in Pond 3 compared to other pools within the Project (Table B2.4,

Figure 2.3). Total phosphorus (TP) was more variable across sampling locations with the highest concentration in Pond 3 (0.11–0.15 mg P/L; Figure 2.3), but was lower than the Sandusky River average of 0.47 mg P/L. This difference in DRP vs. TP concentrations implies that much of the TP was in other forms, such as particulate or organic phosphorus. DRP concentrations didn't vary much seasonally (Table B2.5), but TP was highest in summer and winter (0.13 and 0.103 mg P/L, respectively) compared to fall and spring (0.063 and 0.043 mg P/L, respectively). The consistently low levels of DRP imply that the wetland soils are retaining phosphate and not releasing phosphate even in ideal conditions for release.

In general, across all water samples nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) concentrations tended to be very low, total ammonia (NH₃) was slightly higher, and total nitrogen (TN) was higher than both NO_x and NH₃ (Table 2.1). Typical NO_x concentrations in agricultural surface waters often exceed 1 mg N/L, yet we found concentrations were typically below detection and only reached 1 mg N/L from the one sample we were able to collect from the vernal pool in 2022. In general, NO_x concentrations were lowest in fall (0.008 mg N/L), but similar across other seasons (0.013–0.071 mg N/L; Table B2.7). The highest NH₃ concentrations were found in Ponds 1A and 3B (0.169 and 0.159 mg N/L, respectively), but were otherwise similar on average across sampling locations (0.02–0.035 mg N/L). NH₃ concentrations were somewhat higher in summer and winter (0.049 and 0.042 mg N/L, respectively) compared to fall and spring (0.029 and 0.03 mg N/L, respectively; Table B2.7). Interestingly, TN was far higher than dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN = NO_x+NH₃) indicating that total organic N was a large contributor of N to these ponds. TN was highest in Pond 3 (1.286 mg N/L) and the one sample from the vernal pool (2.23 mg N/L) and tended to be higher in summer (1.536 mg N/L).

Aside from N concentrations, concentrations of chloride and sulfate were also much lower than typically expected in surface or groundwater. On average, chloride concentrations were 3.6 mg/L and sulfate concentrations were 4.8 mg/L (data not shown) across all sampling locations and times. In comparison, the Sandusky River averaged 41.3 mg/L of chloride and 87.3 mg/L of sulfate in 2023. The National Atmospheric Deposition Program (NADP) found rainwater for this region in 2022 was 0.10 mg/L for chloride and 0.16 mg/L for sulfate. Although these are far lower than what we found in the sampling locations, this implies that much of the input to the project is from precipitation or groundwater upwelling rather than agricultural runoff. In the upcoming sampling season we will be able to monitor groundwater wells to confirm these contributions.

Soil Nutrient Status

Similar to surface water quality, soil parameters tended to be low throughout the project. Soil conductivity ranged from 20–141 µS/cm with the highest conductivity in Pond 1C (Table B2.8). While these levels are lower than other projects, they were similar to the Oakwoods Wetland Project which is also an isolated wetland complex. Soil pH was above neutral (7.14–7.75) at all ponds except for Ponds 1B, 2, and 3B where pH was slightly below neutral (6.2–6.9; Table B2.8). Mehlich 3-extractable phosphorus (M3-P) was low across all sampling locations (0.92–

18.6 mg P/kg; Tables B2.10 and B2.11) and far lower than typical agricultural fields (~30 mg P/kg). Pond 1B and 1C had notably higher M3-P (18.6 and 13.6 mg P/kg, respectively) compared to other sampling locations (< 8.4 mg P/kg, Table B2.10). That said, Mehlich 3-extractable Fe (M3-Fe) and Al (M3-Al) were much more variable across sampling locations (39.7–1691 mg Fe/kg; 27.8–783 mg Al/kg) but tended to vary similarly (i.e., when M3-Fe was high, so was M3-Al). The SPSC was positive in all soils indicating a capacity to sorb phosphate (4.5–170 mg P/kg, Table B2.10, B2.11). Pond 1A had the lowest SPSC (4.5 mg P/kg) and also had the lowest M3-P, M3-Fe, and M3-Al (0.915 mg P/kg, 39.7 mg Fe/kg, and 27.8 mg Al/kg).

Water extractable phosphate ($\text{H}_2\text{O-PO}_4$), nitrate ($\text{H}_2\text{O-NO}_3$), and ammonia ($\text{H}_2\text{O-NH}_3$) were very low across all sampling locations and frequently were below detection (Table B2.12, B2.13). Soil TN and TP were also below detection in the Pond 1 complex and ranged from 900–1684 mg N/kg for TN and 650–715 mg P/kg for TP in the other ponds (Table B2.12). Pond 3B had the highest $\text{H}_2\text{O-PO}_4$, TN, and TP, whereas Ponds 2 and 4 were similar for TN and TP.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

In the coming year, we plan to start consistently monitoring groundwater in 4 wells installed on the property. This should help us better delineate the contributions to surface water (precipitation vs. groundwater). In addition, researchers have depth sensors continuously logging data that will be interpreted in the coming year to calculate the total volume of water stored in the project.

Non-Focal Projects: Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve (FRUW)

Figure 2.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table 2.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Pond 1A	0.026 \pm 0.1	7 (0)	0–0.18	0.066 \pm 0.1	7 (0)	0.01–0.17	1.133 \pm 0.7	7 (0)	0.27–2.1
02. Pond 1B	0 \pm 0	7 (0)	0–0	0.029 \pm 0	7 (1)	0–0.09	1.076 \pm 0.6	7 (0)	0.57–2.25
03. Pond 1C	0.019 \pm 0	7 (0)	0–0.13	0.024 \pm 0	7 (1)	0–0.06	0.846 \pm 0.4	7 (0)	0.49–1.39
04. Pond 1D	0 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0	0.02 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.03	0.637 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	0.37–0.79
05. Pond 2	0 \pm 0	12 (0)	0–0	0.035 \pm 0	12 (0)	0.01–0.11	1.161 \pm 0.7	12 (1)	0–2.91
06. Pond 3A	0 \pm 0	9 (0)	0–0	0.026 \pm 0	9 (0)	0.01–0.05	1.286 \pm 0.4	9 (0)	0.78–2.08
07. Pond 3B	0 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0	0.096 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.01–0.16	0.333 \pm 0.4	3 (1)	0–0.74
08. Pond 4	0.021 \pm 0.1	12 (0)	0–0.16	0.024 \pm 0	12 (1)	0–0.07	0.777 \pm 0.5	12 (2)	0–1.57
09. Vernal Pool A	1 \pm NA	1 (0)	1–1	0.046 \pm NA	1 (0)	0.05–0.05	2.23 \pm NA	1 (0)	2.23–2.23

Figure 2.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Fruth Wetland Nature Preserve project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration (MERW)

Project Overview

Mercer County

Partner: Lake Facilities Authority

ODNR Description: “There are several complimentary wetland restoration projects planned at Mercer Wildlife Area, all with the goal of limiting nutrient loading into Grand Lake St Marys. The Division of Wildlife will enhance a forested wetland to help with nutrient filtering. The project will also upgrade a pump and supply lines to a newly created wetland increasing the volume of water from Grand Lake St. Marys that can be treated.”³

Management Considerations

This Project is vulnerable to vegetation invasion from adjacent non-state properties, as there are nearby populations of Phragmites. Continued visual inspection of the vegetation community by the Base Crew will detect invasion and can alert managers if actions need to be taken.

Sampling Approach

The Mercer Wetland Complex is being restored in multiple phases (Figure 3.1). Construction on Phases 1 and 2 was completed in 2023, and these portions of the Project have been routinely monitored since 2023. In the Phase 1 portion of the Project, water from Grand Lake St. Marys is pumped into a series of field tiles as a water source for a corn/soybean field. The water level in the field is controlled using two water control structures (WCS). Water from the field tiles then flows into a series of three wetland pools. These pools are connected by tile with water level controlled by WCS before outflowing back into Grand Lake St. Marys. For Phase 2, water from Grand Lake St. Marys is also the inflow source being pumped into one of two wetland pools. The two pools are connected by tile and the water level is controlled by WCS. Outflow from pool two is directed into a forested floodplain in which water level is also controlled using a WCS before outflowing into Grand Lake St. Marys. Water samples are collected from Grand Lake St. Marys, the outflow pools, and each pool in the complex (9 sampling locations, Figure 3.1) to be able to assess the nutrient reduction efficiency of each phase.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Lake Inflow Phase 1 had the greatest average manually measured water depth (36 cm) while Pool 1 Outflow Phase 1 has the lowest amongst all sampling locations (7 cm; Table B3.2). Pool 3 (forest) Outflow Phase 2 had the greatest variability and the greatest water depth (74 cm) amongst all sampling locations (Figure 3.2, Table B3.2). The discrete, manually-collected water depths shown in Figure 3.2 and Tables B3.2–B3.3 represent the water depths at the location where water samples were collected, which are not always representative of the deepest location

³ “Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/mercero-wildlife-area-wetland-restoration-projects/>

within a wetland feature. Therefore, average water depths at the deepest pool location may at times be greater than reported given that access to the deepest point of some wetland pools is not always safely feasible.

Sampling Locations

- 01. Lake Inflow Phase 1
- 02. Post Field Phase 1
- 03. Pool 1 Outflow
- 04. Pool 2 Outflow
- 05. Pool 3 Outflow
- 06. Lake Inflow Phase 2
- 07. Pool 1 Outflow Phase 2
- 08. Pool 3 (forest) Outflow Phase 2
- 09. Pool 2 Outflow Phase 2

Figure 3.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point. Note that the inflow for Phases 1 and 2 (locations 01 and 06) are the same.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Pool 3 (forest) Outflow Phase 2 had the greatest average concentration of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) among both Phase 1 and Phase 2 sampling locations (0.101 and 0.705 mg P/L, respectively; Table B3.4). There is currently no vegetation in Phase 2, and as it establishes it may store some of the inflowing phosphorus (P) in its biomass. Average DRP and TP concentrations were higher for Post Field (0.094 and 0.345 mg P/L, respectively) than Lake Inflow (0.056 and 0.329 mg P/L, respectively) in Phase 1 (Table B3.4). Average TP concentrations decreased from Post Field Phase 1 to the Pool 3 Outflow (0.345 and 0.229 mg P/L, respectively), but it gradually increased from pool to pool (Pool 1–Pool 3; Table B3.4).

Average nitrate+nitrite (NOx) and total nitrogen (TN) concentrations in Phase 1 decreased by 99% and 34% between the Lake Inflow Phase 1 and Pool 3 Outflow (Table 3.1). On average, NOx and TN concentrations at Lake Inflow Phase 2 decreased by 24% and 16% upon reaching the Pool 3 (forest) Outflow Phase 2 (Table 3.1). Average NOx and TN concentrations were highest in the spring, while average DRP and TP concentrations were highest in the summer (Tables B3.5 and B3.7).

Figure 3.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil data not available for the 2023 Annual Report.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

Soil sample analysis seems critical to help explain large variations in surface water nutrient concentrations in the Mercer Wetland Complex. Analysis of soil samples collected in 2023 is pending and will provide additional information specific to Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC). Installation of continuously logging water depth sensors will support more robust surveillance of hydrologic conditions and estimates of input and output water volumes at this project to support assessment of nutrient function. Finally, Phase 1 at the Mercer Wetland Complex could represent a unique opportunity to assess treatment of nutrients via crop uptake of nutrients given it is structured as a kind of water recycling system in which nutrient laden water is pumped into subsurface tiles in a corn/soybean crop rotation field.

Non-Focal Projects: Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration (MERW)

Figure 3.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Non-Focal Projects: Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration (MERW)

Table 3.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Mercer Wetland Complex Restoration project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Lake Inflow Phase 1	0.695 ± 1.2	9 (4)	0–3.24	0.331 ± 0.1	3 (0)	0.23–0.45	4.177 ± 0.6	9 (0)	3.51–5.09
02. Post Field Phase 1	0.069 ± 0.1	3 (2)	0–0.21	NA	NA	NA	3.686 ± 1.5	3 (0)	2.06–4.94
03. Pool 1 Outflow	0.339 ± 0.7	4 (1)	0–1.33	0.048 ± 0	2 (0)	0.04–0.06	2.234 ± 0.1	4 (0)	2.07–2.39
04. Pool 2 Outflow	0.688 ± 1.4	8 (3)	0–3.99	0.082 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0.04–0.12	2.745 ± 0.9	8 (0)	1.69–4.53
05. Pool 3 Outflow	0.003 ± 0	8 (6)	0–0.01	0.022 ± 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.03	2.736 ± 1	8 (0)	1.43–4.44
06. Lake Inflow Phase 2	0.022 ± 0	3 (0)	0.02–0.03	NA	NA	NA	3.52 ± 0.2	3 (0)	3.39–3.74
07. Pool 1 Outflow Phase 2	0.5 ± 0.4	3 (0)	0.02–0.78	NA	NA	NA	2.682 ± 0.8	3 (0)	1.82–3.39
08. Pool 3 (forest) Outflow Phase 2	0.014 ± 0	4 (1)	0–0.02	NA	NA	NA	2.956 ± 1.9	4 (0)	0.77–4.92
09. Pool 2 Outflow Phase 2	0.857 ± NA	1 (0)	0.86–0.86	NA	NA	NA	2.116 ± NA	1 (0)	2.12–2.12

North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration (NORR)

Project Overview

Ottawa County | Packer Creek Watershed | Inland

Project size: 23 Acres

Partner: Ducks Unlimited

ODNR Description: “This Project added a pump and protective structures to capture and filter the runoff from over 60-acres of adjacent agricultural drainage. H₂Ohio funding was leveraged with federal sources create additional water-quality benefits from a Lake Erie CREP emergent marsh restoration along Packer Creek. Construction was completed in fall 2021.”⁴

Management Considerations

The North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration Project (hereafter North Ridge Project) has potential for nutrient retention due to its hydrologic structure, which captures tile drainage from nearby agricultural land use, holds it within the wetland, and then releases it into Packer Creek. However, the duration of water retention needed for nutrient sequestration in the wetland complex is not yet defined. Given the importance of water level and connectivity information to elucidate wetland nutrient retention, accurate and prompt reporting of water level management actions (e.g., via Survey123 or email) in the North Ridge Project (i.e., when and to what extent water control structures (WCS) are used, like the pump) allows researchers to document water level and physicochemical changes in the wetland pool and ultimately derive better estimates of nutrient retention.

Sampling Approach

Agricultural tiles drain into the ditch that borders the Project on the north and east sides. Nutrient-rich ditch water is then pumped into the wetland complex, where it can reside before being released into Packer Creek via a water level control structure (AgriDrain). The sampling approach aims to assess and compare nutrient concentrations within the ditch, in separate wetland pools, and within Packer Creek (Figure 4.1).

⁴ “North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/gatorland-wetland-restoration-phase-2/>

Sampling Locations

- 01. Ditch Pump
- 02. WCS
- 03. Packer Creek
- 04. West Pool
- 05. North Dike
- 06. East Pool
- 07. North Ditch
- 08. East Ditch
- 09. Center

Figure 4.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Sampling Location Water Depths

The North Ditch had the greatest mean water depth (116 cm), which was likely driven by a few high (> 100 cm) depth values in the summer and variability due to runoff from rain events (Figure 4.2, Table B4.2). The Center pool is the deepest within the wetland and shows the highest median water level (Figure 4.2).

Non-Focal Projects: North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration (NORR)

Figure 4.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Ditch Pump and WCS had the greatest mean dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) concentration (0.076 mg P/L), while Center and West Pool had the lowest (0.002 and 0.005 mg P/L, respectively; Table B4.4). Except for Center and West Pool (0.027–0.030 mg P/L), all sampling locations had similar average total phosphorus (TP) concentrations (0.115–0.228 mg P/L; Table B4.4). The Center and West Pool locations are the farthest from the flow of ditch water, thus biogeochemical processes that influence nutrient cycles have had more time to take place. Conversely, the sampling locations within and near the ditch (i.e., Ditch Pump, WCS, North Ditch, and East Ditch) had the greatest observed ranges and mean concentrations of TP due to nutrient rich tile drainage (Table B4.4). Ditch Pump had the greatest mean TP concentration (0.228 ± 0.3 mg P/L), possibly due to resuspension and turbation from pump flow (Table B4.4). Additionally, East Ditch had the greatest maximum TP concentration observed (1.048 mg P/L) in 2023. (Table B4.4). Interestingly, DRP and TP concentrations were most variable in June and July 2022, possibly due to rain events and management actions (Figure 4.3).

As expected, because they drain agricultural-dominated landscapes, North Ditch, East Ditch, and Ditch Pump had the greatest mean total nitrogen (TN) and nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) concentrations (Table 4.1). Like TP concentrations, total ammonia (NH₃) concentrations were similar among all sites (0.105–0.227 mg N/L) except for West Pool, North Dike, and Center (0.039–0.046 mg N/L), likely due to their distance from the tile drainage source (Table 4.1).

Note that East Pool results are omitted from this discussion due to a limited sample size. The East Pool is an ephemeral pool with limited and variable inundation. With the data provided, there seems to be preliminary evidence of nutrient retention, as concentrations are lower in the Center and West Pools. Biogeochemical processes like sorption, vegetation uptake and sedimentation are likely explanations for nutrient retention once ditch water reaches these pools in the wetland complex.

Soil Nutrient Status

Ditch Pump, WCS, and West Pool had similar mean soil pH (7.1–7.3) and conductivity (1256–1553 μ S/cm), but North Dike must be omitted due to a sample size of n=1 (Table B4.8). Ditch Pump, WCS, and West Pool had similar Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) values (87.8 ± 34.1 , 67 ± 46.3 , and 78 ± 29.9 mg P/kg, respectively), while differences in Mehlich 3-extracted phosphorus (M3-P), iron (M3-Fe), and aluminum (M3-Al) were observed (Table B4.10). For example, WCS had much higher M3-P concentration compared to the Ditch Pump and West Pool, but high concentrations of iron (M3-Fe) balanced out the soil sorption capacity for phosphate. These results show that there is capacity to sorb phosphate at these three sampling locations (Figure 4.4).

Ditch Pump had slightly higher water extractable phosphate (H₂O-PO₄) concentration on average, but overall H₂O-PO₄ was similar between sites (0.962–2.393 mg P/kg, Table B4.12). Ditch Pump also had the highest average water extractable nitrate (H₂O-NO₃), while WCS has

the highest average water extractable ammonia ($\text{H}_2\text{O-NH}_3$) concentrations (11.89 and 10.37 mg N/kg, respectively, Table B4.12). WCS had the highest and most variable soil TN and TP among the sampling locations (Table B4.12).

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

Starting in 2024, researchers will install additional markers throughout the Project to standardize sampling locations where water depth is recorded and increase the repeatability of depth measurements. Sampling visits at this and other H2Ohio Projects will be conducted at a reduced frequency (once per season) in an effort to prioritize data management and communication of relevant and useful data products across the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program.

Non-Focal Projects: North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration (NORR)

Figure 4.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Non-Focal Projects: North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration (NORR)

Table 4.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Ditch Pump	3.732 ± 11.9	14 (0)	0–44.78	0.19 ± 0.4	14 (0)	0.02–1.64	5.125 ± 12.4	14 (0)	0–47.83
02. WCS	0.756 ± 2.4	15 (0)	0–9.24	0.105 ± 0.1	15 (0)	0.02–0.52	2.278 ± 2.3	15 (0)	0.83–10.4
03. Packer Creek	1.816 ± 2.8	15 (0)	0–10.74	0.227 ± 0.3	15 (0)	0.01–1.4	3.026 ± 2.9	15 (0)	0.92–12.69
04. West Pool	0.038 ± 0	16 (0)	0–0.1	0.039 ± 0	16 (0)	0.01–0.08	0.814 ± 0.1	16 (0)	0.52–0.95
05. North Dike	0.038 ± 0	11 (0)	0–0.15	0.046 ± 0	11 (0)	0.02–0.1	1.294 ± 0.4	11 (0)	0.9–1.98
06. East Pool	0.093 ± NA	1 (0)	0.09–0.09	0.08 ± NA	1 (0)	0.08–0.08	0.7 ± NA	1 (0)	0.7–0.7
07. North Ditch	4.053 ± 13.5	16 (0)	0–54.46	0.134 ± 0.3	16 (0)	0.02–1.21	5.161 ± 13.4	16 (0)	0.73–55.33
08. East Ditch	4.671 ± 12.7	13 (0)	0.04–46.54	0.21 ± 0.4	13 (0)	0.03–1.54	5.597 ± 12.4	13 (0)	0.87–46.52
09. Center	0.036 ± 0	11 (0)	0.02–0.06	0.04 ± 0	11 (0)	0.03–0.06	0.798 ± 0.1	11 (0)	0.56–0.93

Figure 4.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the North Ridge Hunt Club Wetland Restoration project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration (OOPR)

Project Overview

Lucas County | Maumee River Watershed

Project size: 48 Acres

Partners: Metroparks Toledo

ODNR Description: “The existing Toledo Metroparks Oak Openings Preserve converted previously farmed land adjacent to the preserve into wetlands. Restoration of the property included regrading and creating wetland habitat. Forested wetlands and prairie habitat was also to be added along Ai Creek, a tributary in the Maumee Basin.”⁵

Management Considerations

There are no water control structures or systems in this Project, and no management considerations at this time. However, the design and construction team modified the structure and size of wetland pools 12–15 on the east side of the Project due to the severe erosion that occurred after a heavy storm soon after construction was complete in 2021. The wetland pools were enlarged and berms were constructed between them so they hold and process more water. No additional changes to the Project have been made nor are any anticipated.

Sampling Approach

The original construction of the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project (hereafter Oak Openings Preserve) was completed in 2021 and later modifications were completed in 2022. Water samples are collected approximately once per season and soil samples once per year. Oak Openings Preserve consists of eleven geographically isolated wetland (GIW) pools (Wetland Pools 1–11 in Figure 5.1) and four pools that serve as a treatment train (Wetland Pools 12–15 in Figure 5.1), treating water that is flowing down gradient across the surface of the Project on the east side. The Project is close to Ai Creek, which connects to Swan Creek and eventually to the Maumee River. The hydrologic connection between the pools of this Project and Ai Creek is unclear and, at most, transient, occurring only during a brief period of the year. The main inputs are probably rainfall and surface runoff, and potentially transient connection to a drainage ditch to the west of the site during heavy rain. In 2023, water samples were collected from each of the wetland pools listed in Figure 5.1 when standing water was present. Soil samples were collected from within each pool and from upland areas near the pools for comparison.

⁵ “Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/oak-openings-preserve-metropark-expansion/>

Sampling Locations

- 01. Wetland Pool 1
- 02. Wetland Pool 2
- 03. Wetland Pool 3
- 04. Wetland Pool 4
- 05. Wetland Pool 5
- 06. Wetland Pool 6
- 07. Wetland Pool 7
- 08. Wetland Pool 8
- 09. Wetland Pool 9
- 10. Wetland Pool 10
- 11. Wetland Pool 11
- 12. Wetland Pool 12
- 13. Wetland Pool 13
- 14. Wetland Pool 14
- 15. Wetland Pool 15

Figure 5.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Figure 5.2. Wetland Pool 15 at the ‘top’ of the treatment train at Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project on July 11, 2023, facing south. (Genna Hunt)

Sampling Location Water Depths

Most of the pools at Oak Openings Preserve remained relatively shallow (< 0.5 m) and had comparable depths (Table B5.2, Figure 5.3). The wetland pools at this Project experienced seasonal inundation. Pools filled with water over winter and spring (up to 45 cm) then became dry through the summer and fall (0–25 cm; Table B5.3). Since 2023 was an especially dry year, some pools that may normally remain inundated year-round became dry, particularly Pool 12 at the bottom of the treatment train. The deepest water at this Project was typically in the treatment train (Pools 12–15), especially Pool 12 (up to 45 cm) and Pool 3 (up to 40 cm) on the west side of the Project (Table B5.2, Figure 5.3). Water depth measurements were generally taken at sampling locations within pools, not always at the deepest point within pools.

Non-Focal Projects: Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration (OOPR)

Figure 5.3. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

The highest surface water total phosphorous (TP) concentrations observed were in the geographically clustered Pools 2–5 (0.9–1.4 mg P/L measured in fall 2021). However, Pool 3, also located within this cluster, had some of the lowest TP concentrations (0.073 ± 0.1 mg P/L; Table B5.4). Average TP concentrations in the treatment train Pools 13, 14, and 15 were comparable (0.107–0.158 mg P/L; Table B5.4) while Pool 12, the lowest pool in the train, had higher concentrations (0.354 mg P/L; Table B5.4). TP concentrations, overall, were highest in fall (0.605 ± 0.6 mg P/L) and lowest in spring (0.052 ± 0 mg P/L; Table B5.5). The highest

dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) concentrations were measured in winter in Pools 1, 12, and 15 (Table B5.4, Figure 5.4). Total nitrogen (TN) concentrations were much higher on average in Pools 10 and 12 (11.534 ± 18.5 and 7.07 ± 19.3 mg N/L, respectively) than any other pools, but also had very high variability (Table 5.1). TN concentrations, like TP concentrations, were highest in fall and lowest in spring (Table B5.7).

Soil Nutrient Status

There was a very wide range of Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) at this Project across wetland pools (Figure 5.5). Some pools (e.g., Pools 15 and 14 at the beginning of the treatment train) had high SPSC (Table B5.10), which indicates higher capacity to sorb phosphorus (P). However, other samples taken near the bottom of the treatment train (Pool 12) and especially near Pools 5 and 2 had very low average SPSC (< 35 mg P/kg; Figure 5.5, Table B5.10). Mehlich 3-extracted P (M3-P) was somewhat high in some parts of this Project (> 150 mg P/kg). Water-extractable phosphate (H_2O-PO_4) was also high for the soil in some locations (Table B5.12), and these areas may be at risk of releasing P. Average soil conductivity was highest in Pool 3 by a large margin ($950.5 \mu S/cm$; Table B5.8) and once again stood out from the nearby cluster of Pools 2–5. Pool 5 also had one instance of average conductivity relative to the rest of the surrounding pools and one instance of values much higher and more comparable to those found in Pool 3 (Table B5.8).

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

Continued monitoring of hydrology and water chemistry will help researchers identify source(s) of water to pools at Oak Openings. In the coming year, we will install five water depth sensors to surveil hydrology and estimate of total input and output water volumes to the project treatment train and, ultimately, nutrient load reduction estimates.

Non-Focal Projects: Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration (OOPR)

Figure 5.4. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Non-Focal Projects: Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration (OOPR)

Table 5.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0 ± 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.16 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0.12–0.2	0.805 ± 0.3	2 (0)	0.56–1.05
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.163 ± 0.2	3 (1)	0–0.42	0.099 ± 0.1	3 (1)	0–0.23	1.734 ± 2.3	3 (0)	0.2–4.42
03. Wetland Pool 3	0.146 ± 0.2	5 (1)	0–0.48	0.05 ± 0.1	5 (3)	0–0.2	0.656 ± 0.6	4 (0)	0.3–1.51
04. Wetland Pool 4	0.298 ± 0.4	2 (1)	0–0.6	0.138 ± 0.2	2 (0)	0–0.28	2.442 ± 2.6	2 (0)	0.6–4.28
05. Wetland Pool 5	0.409 ± 0.7	3 (1)	0–1.17	0.11 ± 0.2	3 (1)	0–0.29	3.519 ± 3.8	3 (0)	0.67–7.86
06. Wetland Pool 6	0.606 ± 1	3 (1)	0–1.75	0.107 ± 0.1	3 (1)	0–0.25	2.483 ± 3.6	3 (0)	0.29–6.63
07. Wetland Pool 7	0.549 ± 0.7	5 (1)	0–1.72	0.048 ± 0	5 (1)	0–0.09	4.68 ± 9.3	5 (0)	0.37–21.3
08. Wetland Pool 8	0.054 ± 0	3 (1)	0–0.09	0.099 ± 0.1	3 (1)	0–0.26	0.789 ± 0.7	3 (0)	0.18–1.58
09. Wetland Pool 9	0.435 ± 0.7	3 (1)	0–1.24	0.112 ± 0.1	3 (1)	0–0.27	3.132 ± 4.5	3 (0)	0.41–8.3
10. Wetland Pool 10	0.212 ± 0.3	3 (1)	0–0.57	0.378 ± 0.5	3 (0)	0.04–0.97	11.534 ± 18.5	3 (0)	0.49–32.92
12. Wetland Pool 12	0.229 ± 0.2	12 (2)	0–0.58	0.052 ± 0.1	12 (6)	0–0.36	7.07 ± 19.3	11 (0)	0.28–65.28
13. Wetland Pool 13	0.186 ± 0.2	9 (1)	0–0.5	0.09 ± 0.2	9 (5)	0–0.63	0.595 ± 0.5	8 (0)	0.2–1.51
14. Wetland Pool 14	3.153 ± 5.3	3 (0)	0.06–9.28	0.088 ± 0.1	3 (0)	0.03–0.13	3.737 ± 6	3 (0)	0.22–10.63

Non-Focal Projects: Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration (OOPR)

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
15. Wetland Pool 15	0.03 ± 0	2 (1)	0–0.06	0.054 ± 0	2 (0)	0.04–0.07	0.585 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0.53–0.64

Figure 5.5. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Oak Openings Preserve Wetland Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Otsego Schools, Wood County (OTSS)

Project Overview

Wood County

Project Size: 13 Acres

Partner: Black Swamp Conservancy

ODNR Description: “The Otsego School District Living Laboratory Project will restore natural habitat on a 16-acre previously farmed site located in Wood County. Restoration of this site will include 2.5 acres of riparian (wooded) habitat and 5 to 10.5 acres of wetland habitat. This project will maximize sediment and nutrient capture from the 13.38 square mile watershed. Once complete, Black Swamp Conservancy will transfer the Project to Otsego Schools for use as a living laboratory. Approximately 1.5 acres of the property will be retained in agricultural use for Otsego School’s Future Farmers of America program to demonstrate the value of using natural habitats to filter agricultural runoff.”⁶

Management Considerations

The Otsego School District Living Laboratory Project is a wetland used primarily for educational purposes. Although the project lacks structures for active hydrologic management, its unique inclusion of a small agricultural field directly adjacent to the wetland project provides unique opportunities to test drivers of the agricultural-wetland system function collectively and may provide insights into the functioning of larger, similar systems. The soils at the Otsego Project are highly permeable and have moderate phosphate sorption capacity, indicating a pre-existing capacity to retain nutrients through infiltration of water through the sandy soils and sorption of phosphate to soil particles. However, continued monitoring can reveal if nutrients are being successfully processed or translocated into groundwater, where they may accumulate and become a source to downslope groundwater-fed streams and wetlands.

Sampling Approach

Water samples are collected approximately once per season and include the east and west sides of the Emergent Wetland, Tontogany Creek, and a representative set of hollow pools on the east, south, and west sides of the agricultural field (Root Wad Hollow, SE Hollow, Vernal Pool, Deadwood Hollow; Figure 6.1). Soil samples are collected in the experimental agricultural field, in the same locations where water samples are collected, and in the food forest between the agricultural field and the emergent wetland, in the wet meadow, and in upland areas in the meadow.

This Project has a unique feature: a small agricultural field intended for use by students, surrounded by wetlands. This offers a special opportunity to examine the interaction of agricultural drainage and wetlands. The presence of the agricultural field and the agricultural

⁶ “Otsego School District Living Laboratory Project.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/otsego-school-district-living-laboratory-project/>

practices employed will be considered in the interpretation of data collected on the wetland function. This Project is also unique regarding its location within 100 feet of Otsego Local Schools, a medium size rural school system. The school administration and teachers are very enthusiastic about using the wetlands for enhancing student learning and have conducted a variety of activities in the Project. We are exploring establishing connections to existing community science platforms like Crowd Hydrology and Chronology to engage local K-12 students in collecting data to support monitoring at this Project.

- Sampling Locations**
- 01. Emergent Wetland West
 - 02. Tontogany Creek
 - 03. Emergent Wetland East
 - 04. Root Wad Hollow
 - 05. SE Hollow
 - 06. Vernal Pool
 - 07. Deadwood Hollow
 - 08. West Tributary
 - 09. Meadow
 - 10. Food Forest
 - 11. Agricultural Field
 - 12. Center Hollow
 - 13. Wet Meadow
 - 14. West Hollow

Figure 6.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Otsego Schools, Wood County project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Sampling Location Water Depths

The Emergent Wetlands tended to stay relatively shallow (0–18 cm) while the hummock-hollow pools (located across the southern and southeastern parts of the Project) and the Vernal Pool tended to be deeper (0–40 cm) and more consistently inundated (Table B6.2, Figure 6.2). Water depth measurements were generally taken at sampling locations within pools, not always at the deepest point within pools.

Non-Focal Projects: Otsego Schools, Wood County (OTSS)

Figure 6.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) concentrations were lowest in the Vernal Pool, the Deadwood Hollow, and Emergent Wetland West (0 mg P/L at all locations). The highest average DRP concentrations were in the West Tributary (0.15 mg P/L, but only one sample collected) followed by the Root Wad Hollow (0.09 mg P/L; Table B6.4). Total phosphorus (TP) concentrations were on average lowest in the Vernal Pool (0.03 mg P/L), the Deadwood Hollow (0.04 mg P/L), and the Root Wad Hollow (0.09 mg P/L), while the highest observed average TP concentrations were in the SE Hollow (0.4 mg P/L) and Emergent Wetland East (0.3 mg P/L; Table B6.4).

Total ammonia (NH₃) was zero or below detection limit in all except one sampling location (Tontogany Creek; Table 6.1). The highest nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) concentrations observed were in Tontogany Creek (1.2 mg N/L), followed by the West Tributary (0.7 mg N/L, but only one sample collected), and the Emergent Wetland East (0.6 mg N/L; Table 6.1). Total nitrogen (TN) concentrations were on average highest in Tontogany Creek (2.3 mg N/L) followed closely by the SE Hollow (2.1 mg N/L; Table 6.1). The Vernal Pool had the lowest concentrations for both TN (0.7 mg N/L) and NO_x (0 mg N/L; Table 6.1).

Soil Nutrient Status

Highest soil pH observed were in Emergent Wetland East (8.1) and Tontogany Creek (8.0; Table B6.8). Lowest soil pH were in the Wet Meadow (6.4) and the Center Hollow (4.7; Table B6.8). Mehlich 3-extracted phosphorus (M3-P) values throughout the Project ranged from 12 to 52 mg P/kg, with most around 20 mg P/kg. The Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) values were moderate to high (65+ mg P/kg) in most locations in this Project (Figure 6.4). One location, the Food Forest, had lower SPSC (28 mg P/kg), but it is due to low iron and aluminum likely because the soil has high loam content as indicated by the USDA NRCS soil map for this location. Total nitrogen (TN) levels in the soil samples were low to moderate throughout the Project.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

Water level sensors will be deployed in the emergent wetland pools at the north end of the Project to detect flooding events and assess this wetland's function as a floodplain wetland. Researchers will continue to sample representative hollows for surface water nutrient concentrations periodically.

Figure 6.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table 6.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Emergent Wetland West	0.318 ± 0.4	3 (0)	0.09–0.74	0 ± 0	3 (3)	0–0	1.035 ± 0.7	2 (0)	0.56–1.51
02. Tontogany Creek	1.176 ± 1.2	5 (0)	0.31–3.12	0.037 ± 0	5 (1)	0–0.1	2.258 ± 2.1	3 (0)	0.86–4.67
03. Emergent Wetland East	0.547 ± 0.8	3 (0)	0.06–1.5	0 ± 0	3 (3)	0–0	1.555 ± 1.4	2 (0)	0.57–2.54
04. Root Wad Hollow	0.11 ± 0.1	3 (0)	0.06–0.18	0 ± 0	3 (3)	0–0	1.03 ± 0.3	2 (0)	0.8–1.26
05. SE Hollow	0.05 ± 0	3 (1)	0–0.08	0 ± 0	3 (3)	0–0	2.075 ± 1.9	2 (0)	0.72–3.43
06. Vernal Pool	0 ± 0	2 (2)	0–0	0 ± 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.705 ± 0	2 (0)	0.69–0.72
07. Deadwood Hollow	0.025 ± 0	2 (1)	0–0.05	0 ± 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.815 ± 0	2 (0)	0.8–0.83
08. West Tributary	0.721 ± NA	1 (0)	0.72–0.72	0 ± NA	1 (1)	0–0	1.109 ± NA	1 (0)	1.11–1.11

Figure 6.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Otsego Schools, Wood County Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project (OTTN)

Project Overview

Lucas County | Crane Creek Estuary | Coastal

Project Size: 586.3 Acres

Partner: Ottawa Soil & Water Conservation District

ODNR Description: “This Project reconnects three wetland habitat units to Lake Erie through the Crane Creek Estuary. The 586-acre project will reduce nutrients flowing into the lake by diverting excess water from farmlands in the 57-square mile Crane Creek/Veler Road ditch upstream of the wetland habitats. Project construction was completed in July 2021.”⁷

Management Considerations

Accurate information about wetland water levels and connectivity between wetland units and adjacent waterways is critical to elucidate wetland nutrient retention, particularly in coastal wetland reconnection projects like the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project (hereafter Ottawa NWR Project). Accurate and prompt reporting of water level management actions (e.g., via Survey123 or email) between Veler Ditch and Pool 3 or MS5 will allow researchers to generate actionable data to inform management actions and derive better estimates of nutrient retention. Monitoring Program researchers will continue to engage with wetland managers to develop effective methods to share information about water level management actions.

Sampling Approach

Hydrologically, the Ottawa NWR Project consists of two wetland parcels (Pool 3 and MS5), Veler Ditch, and Crane Creek (Table B7.1, Figure 7.1). The parcels are permanently inundated, open-water wetlands that are surrounded by dike roads. These parcels are hydrologically isolated from Veler Ditch, Crane Creek, and Lake Erie if not for two water control structures (WCS) in Veler Ditch. Veler Ditch flows into Crane Creek and Lake Erie. The Ottawa NWR Project’s sampling approach aims to investigate and compare surface water and soil nutrient concentrations across these bodies of water.

There are seven sampling locations in the Ottawa NWR Project (Figure 7.1) that are grouped into two categories: within wetland pools (hereafter Wetlands, or Pool 3 and MS5) and outside of wetland pools (hereafter Ditch or Creek). The Wetlands consist of four sampling locations: two sampling locations are within Pool 3 (Pool 3 Center and Pool 3 WCS), and two are within MS5 (MS5 Center and MS5 WCS). Pool 3 Center and MS5 Center samples are collected to investigate open-water nutrient concentrations within the wetland parcels, while Pool 3 WCS and MS5 WCS samples are collected to investigate nutrient concentrations near the water control

⁷ “Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnection Projects.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/ottawa-national-wildlife-refuge-wetland-reconnection-projects/>

structures. Pool 3 Veler Ditch, MS5 Veler Ditch, and Crane Creek locations investigate nutrient-rich surface run-off from the surrounding agricultural land use.

Figure 7.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Water depths taken near the WCSs in the Ditch and Wetlands were similar (Table B7.2). Pool 3 Center (48 ± 24 cm) and Crane Creek (58 ± 18 cm) had the deepest water depths on average, as they were farthest from shorelines and the constructed dike roads. However, Veler Ditch had the greatest water depths recorded in summer (78 and 85 cm, respectively; Figure 7.2). Water depth varied ~ 20 cm around the mean throughout the sampling locations in the Project (Table B7.2).

It is important to note that water depth interpretations should be taken with slight caution because variation in the bottom substrate may have influenced the precision of measurements.

For example, sampling locations near the water control structures are characterized by a rocky, uneven substrate and microtopography that made manual water depth measurements fallible in 2023 given the challenge to determine the position of the water-sediment interface. Furthermore, the exact location of the water depth measurements for some sampling locations (i.e., Pool 3 Center and Crane Creek) were not marked *in situ* due to logistical constraints, which added some uncertainty to the measurements. However, the magnitude of potential inaccuracies does not preclude preliminary interpretation of observed patterns.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Veler Ditch samples had the greatest dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) concentrations, spiking in July and August 2023 (Figure 7.3), while Pool 3 Center had the lowest concentration observed (Table B7.4). Due to one sample with high concentration in Fall 2022 (1.598 mg P/L), total phosphorus (TP) concentration in MS5 WCS had the greatest mean (0.197 ± 0.4 mg P/L), the most variability, and the greatest range (0.032–1.598 mg P/L). Pool 3 Center had the lowest TP concentration (Table B7.4). Summer had the greatest DRP concentrations (0.023 ± 0 mg P/L), but Fall saw the greatest mean concentration (0.122 ± 0.3 mg P/L) and maximum observed concentration (1.598 mg P/L) for TP (Table B7.5). Spring had the lowest mean TP concentration (0.084 ± 0 mg P/L).

MS5 Center had the greatest mean nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) concentration (1.609 ± 0.9 mg N/L) and mean total nitrogen (TN) concentration (2.494 ± 1 mg N/L), but a limited sample size (n=2) makes interpretation less certain (Table 7.1). Aside from MS5 Center, TN concentrations were similar across sampling locations. Total ammonia (NH₃) concentrations were similar as well, except for Pool 3 Center that had slightly lower NH₃ concentration (0.029 ± 0 mg N/L). Table B7.7 shows similar NH₃ concentrations across spring, summer, and fall, but spring shows the greatest mean NO_x (0.837 ± 0.9 mg N/L) and TN (1.684 ± 0.9 mg N/L) concentrations.

Figure 7.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Non-Focal Projects: Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project (OTTN)

Figure 7.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Non-Focal Projects: Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnection Project (OTTN)

Table 7.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Pool 3 Center	0.353 ± 0.6	8 (0)	0–1.42	0.029 ± 0	8 (0)	0.02–0.07	1.016 ± 0.7	8 (0)	0.5–2.2
02. Pool 3 Veler Ditch	0.293 ± 0.6	16 (0)	0–2.36	0.053 ± 0	16 (0)	0.01–0.16	1.173 ± 0.8	16 (0)	0.49–3.06
03. Pool 3 WCS	0.261 ± 0.6	17 (0)	0.01–2.37	0.047 ± 0	17 (0)	0–0.14	1.118 ± 0.7	17 (0)	0.45–3.08
04. MS5 Center	1.609 ± 0.9	2 (0)	0.95–2.27	0.045 ± 0	2 (0)	0.02–0.07	2.494 ± 1	2 (0)	1.81–3.18
05. MS5 Veler Ditch	0.317 ± 0.6	15 (0)	0–2.47	0.054 ± 0	15 (0)	0.02–0.13	1.056 ± 0.6	15 (0)	0.52–3.1
06. MS5 WCS	0.257 ± 0.6	16 (0)	0–2.17	0.064 ± 0.1	16 (0)	0–0.2	1.146 ± 0.6	16 (0)	0.72–2.86
07. Crane Creek	0.288 ± 0.4	11 (0)	0–1.4	0.066 ± 0.1	11 (0)	0.02–0.19	1.009 ± 0.4	11 (0)	0.72–1.98

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil samples were collected only at Pool 3 WCS and MS5 WCS. MS5 WCS (7.3 ± 0.3) had a slightly greater soil pH than Pool 3 WCS (6.92 ± 0.2), but Pool 3 WCS had slightly greater soil conductivity (Table B7.8). Pool 3 WCS had greater Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) compared to MS5 WCS (130.25 ± 58.1 and 64 ± 23 mg P/kg, respectively; Figure 7.4) due to greater concentrations of iron (Fe) and aluminum (Al) at Pool 3 WCS (Table B7.10). MS5 WCS had greater average water-extractable phosphate ($\text{H}_2\text{O-PO}_4$) and ammonia ($\text{H}_2\text{O-NH}_3$) than Pool 3 WCS (Table B7.12). Pool 3 WCS had slightly greater mean TN (1170.5 ± 315.9 mg N/kg) and TP (521.75 ± 93.6 mg P/kg) concentrations than those observed in MS5 WCS for TN (934.75 ± 139.2 mg N/kg) and TP (477.5 ± 38.5 mg P/kg).

Figure 7.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge Wetland Reconnections Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle

indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

The Ottawa NWR Project is an important habitat for many species, such as bald eagles (*Haliaeetus leucocephalus*), and the primary management objective is often to create and preserve habitat for wildlife. Continued monitoring will inform management decisions that incorporate nutrient retention function in addition to habitat provisioning, although trade-offs between these goals may exist. Additionally, wetland monitoring at this Project must be scheduled around hunting schedules and the resident eagle nests. Finally, Pool 3 Center and MS5 Center are the most difficult to access due to dense aquatic vegetation, which limited sample sizes in 2023 and further interpretation.

St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection (SJCO)

Project Overview

Williams County | Maumee River Watershed

Project size: 140 Acres

Partners: Black Swamp Conservancy

ODNR Description: “A combination of nutrient reduction practices are included in this project site, which previously had 20-acres in agricultural use. Efforts included decommissioning subsurface drainage tiles, expanding existing wetlands, and the creation of new ones. Native vegetation, including shrubs and sedges, was planted to help hold nutrients on the land, preventing them from entering nearby waterways. A deciduous forest of native trees also will be restored, within which nutrient and sediment-trapping vernal pools will naturally occur.”⁸

Management Considerations

This Project presents a unique opportunity to compare the nutrient reduction benefit and cost efficiency of converting two different land uses: agricultural field and Conservation Reserve Program (CRP) field. The CRP field includes hydric soils that were converted to wetlands and portions that were not disturbed.

The CRP field soil in areas that were not disturbed during wetland construction has very low Mehlich 3-extracted phosphorus (M3-P) content so it would not be a source of phosphorus (P) even if it was not converted to a wetland. The agricultural field soil has higher M3-P content than the CRP field, but low relative to other agricultural fields. Conversion of these fields into flow-through or floodplain wetlands would potentially increase the nutrient retention function of this land because the soil has relatively high Soil Phosphate Storage Capacity (SPSC) so should be able to capture and hold P.

Most of the pools at this Project function as floodplain wetlands briefly when the branches of the St. Joseph River flood (Figure 8.1); otherwise, they hold relatively little water and serve as geographically isolated wetland pools (GIWs) that decrease surface water runoff. However, because the soil P and nitrogen (N) content is so low, there would be very little P and N export in runoff, so this is a minor effect with respect to P and N export reduction.

Further evaluation and comparison of these two sites should improve our understanding about the wetland performance of ag fields relative to CRP fields as isolated wetlands. This could provide information that would be useful for decisions about which types of sites are best for conversion to specific types of wetlands given former land use.

⁸ “St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/st-joseph-confluence/>

Sampling Approach

Construction at this Project was completed in 2021. Nearly all the pools at this Project function primarily as isolated wetlands for most of the year (Figure 8.2). In late winter and early spring, they function as floodplain wetlands when the St. Joseph River overflows its banks (Table B8.2, Figure 8.3). The Project tends to be dry for most of the year.

As a non-focal Project, the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project is sampled only three times per year for water and once per year for soil. This is a very dry Project, so field crews try to sample in early spring when it is most likely to hold water.

Figure 8.1. St. Joseph River West Branch showing variation in water level and turbidity in fall (left, September 29, 2022) and spring (right, April 19, 2023). (Genna Hunt)

Sampling Locations

- 01. Wetland Pool 1
- 02. Wetland Pool 2
- 03. Wetland Pool 3
- 04. Oxbow Wetland
- 05. St Joe River West Branch
- 06. Wetland Pool 4
- 07. Wetland Pool 4 South Lobe
- 08. Wetland Pool 5
- 09. Wetland Pool 5 Extension
- 10. Wetland Pool 6
- 11. Wetland Pool 7
- 12. Wetland Pool 8
- 13. St Joe River East Branch
- 14. Unnamed tributary
- 15. Oxbow off the river near pool 3
- 16. St Joe loop tributary

Figure 8.2. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point. The Project contains two main areas: the Conservation Reserve Program (CRP) field located in the Northwest portion of the Project (locations 1–5, 15), and the “agricultural field” to the Southeast corner (locations 6–14, 16).

Sampling Location Water Depths

Nearly all pools were dry for most of the year (Table B8.2, Figure 8.3). The wetland pools at this Project experienced seasonal inundation. They filled with water over winter and spring then became dry through the summer and fall (Table B8.3). Water depth measurements were generally taken at sampling locations within pools, not always at the deepest point within pools. At least some pools receive seasonal flooding from the St. Joseph River (Table B8.2, Figure 8.3).

Non-Focal Projects: St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection (SJCO)

Figure 8.3. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Few water samples have been collected at this Project because it tends to be dry most of the year, therefore the following results are based on limited data. The Oxbow Wetland had the highest average total phosphorus (TP) concentrations of the wetland pools at this Project (0.179 ± 0.2 mg P/L; Table B8.4). Wetland Pool 4 had the highest average total nitrogen (TN; 1.2 mg N/L) of the wetland pools at this Project, but all pools were on average within the same TN range (0.7–1.2 mg N/L; Table 8.1). Average TN concentrations in the St. Joseph River East (1.2 mg N/L) and West Branches (1.2 mg N/L) were roughly comparable to TN concentrations within the wetland pools (Table 8.1). Both TP and TN average concentrations (0.35 mg P/L and 3.1 mg N/L, respectively) were highest in the summer (Tables B8.5 and B8.7).

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil conductivity and pH in the St. Joseph River West Branch (2500 μ S/cm, 7.9 pH) tended to be higher than the wetland pools (475–1350 μ S/cm, 6.8–7.7 pH; Table B8.8). Pools 6 and 7 had soils just below neutrality with the lowest average pH (6.8), while other sampling locations reached nearly 8.0 (Table B8.8). Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) levels varied throughout the Project but were all positive on average (40–87 mg P/kg), indicating an ability to sorb P (Figure 8.5). TP concentrations in soil samples were comparable across pools throughout the Project ranging from 325–560 mg P/kg (Table B8.12).

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

In the coming year, we plan to install three water depth sensors at this Project. These will support continuous surveillance and collection of water level data and inform estimates of total input and output water volumes.

Continued monitoring of surface water nutrient concentrations, soil status, and water levels will indicate nutrient function at this project. Researchers will target sampling during peak flooding when resources and logistics allow to better understand the degree of flooding and which pools are most often affected.

We plan to estimate the reduction in P export that occurs due to the elimination of surface runoff by construction of the wetland pools and elimination of tile drainage by estimating the P export that occurred when the land was farmed used data from edge-of-field studies of other similar agricultural fields.

Non-Focal Projects: St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection (SJCO)

Figure 8.4. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Non-Focal Projects: St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection (SJCO)

Table 8.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NOx), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.252 ± 0.3	4 (1)	0–0.65	0 ± 0	4 (4)	0–0	0.889 ± 0.2	4 (0)	0.66–1
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.078 ± NA	1 (0)	0.08–0.08	0 ± NA	1 (1)	0–0	0.898 ± NA	1 (0)	0.9–0.9
04. Oxbow Wetland	0.036 ± 0	4 (2)	0–0.07	0.057 ± 0.1	4 (3)	0–0.23	0.951 ± 0.2	3 (0)	0.82–1.13
05. St. Joseph River West Branch	0.405 ± 0.5	9 (3)	0–1.62	0.021 ± 0	9 (7)	0–0.1	1.186 ± 0.5	9 (0)	0.46–2.15
06. Wetland Pool 4	0.022 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.07	0.026 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.08	1.156 ± 0.6	3 (0)	0.51–1.52
07. Wetland Pool 4 South Lobe	0.092 ± NA	1 (0)	0.09–0.09	0 ± NA	1 (1)	0–0	0.858 ± NA	1 (0)	0.86–0.86
08. Wetland Pool 5	0.2 ± 0.3	4 (1)	0–0.65	0 ± 0	4 (4)	0–0	0.676 ± 0.3	4 (0)	0.45–1.06
10. Wetland Pool 6	0.035 ± 0	2 (1)	0–0.07	0.054 ± 0.1	2 (1)	0–0.11	0.862 ± 0.9	2 (0)	0.2–1.52
11. Wetland Pool 7	0.068 ± 0	3 (0)	0.05–0.08	0 ± 0	3 (3)	0–0	0.999 ± 0.4	3 (0)	0.74–1.45
13. St. Joseph River East Branch	0.35 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0.28–0.42	0 ± 0	2 (2)	0–0	1.166 ± 0.2	2 (0)	1.02–1.31
14. Unnamed tributary	0.233 ± 0.2	7 (1)	0–0.7	0.434 ± 0.4	7 (1)	0–0.97	2.058 ± 0.7	7 (0)	1.12–3.05

Non-Focal Projects: St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection (SJCO)

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
16. St. Joseph loop tributary	0.046 ± 0	2 (0)	0.04–0.06	0.252 ± 0.4	2 (1)	0–0.5	2.91 ± 2.3	2 (0)	1.3–4.52

Figure 8.5. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the St. Joseph Confluence Wetland Reconnection Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands (SPRC)

Project Overview

Miami County

Project Size: 40 acres

Partners: Miami County Park District

ODNR Description: “The Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands project is a 14-acre off-channel wetland restoration project. The project site is located in a 40-acre field that had been previously planted with trees and shrubs through the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) Partners for Fish and Wildlife (PFW) Program in partnership with the property landowner, and the Miami County Park District (MCPD). Restoration of the off-channel wetlands will filter floodwaters from the Great Miami River and Spring Creek during high water events and reduce in-stream energy. Fish and wildlife habitat will also be improved by wetland habitat for native fishes, macroinvertebrates, migratory birds, and reptiles/amphibians.”⁹

Management Considerations

Lowering the inflow notch would facilitate more opportunity for additional water to enter this floodplain wetland.

Sampling Approach

Construction of the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands was completed in 2021 and monitoring began right after construction. Water from the Great Miami River can enter the wetland through an inflow notch into a large floodplain pool (South Pool, Figure 9.1) when the river reaches a discharge of 5,529 cubic feet per second (CFS). Water from Spring Creek can also enter the wetland through an inflow notch in a separate floodplain pool (North Pool, Figure 9.1). The two floodplain pools were designed to be connected through a channel allowing water from the Spring Creek pool to enter the Great Miami River pool. However, this central channel seems to have largely filled in, rendering the pools disconnected so far as surface flows. Surface water samples are collected monthly and soil samples are collected annually from upstream Spring Creek, upstream and downstream Great Miami River, and a few areas within the wetland to assess the nutrient load being reduced from the Great Miami River.

⁹ “Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/springcreek-confluence-off-channel-wetlands/>

Non-Focal Projects: Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands (SPRC)

Sampling Locations

- 01. Spring Creek
- 02. North Pool
- 03. Connecting Channel
- 04. South Pool
- 05. Great Miami River Downstream
- 06. Great Miami River Upstream
- 07. Great Miami River Downstream at Barbie Park

Figure 9.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point. Sampling locations 6 and 7 in the Great Miami River are just off the map to the Northwest and South for the upstream and downstream (at Barbie Park) points, respectively.

Figure 9.2. Images of the same wetland pool at Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project from October 2023 and January 2024 showing drastic changes in water level over a three-month period.

Sampling Location Water Depths

North Pool had the greatest water depth on average (50 ± 19 cm), but South Pool had a slightly broader range of water depths (8–91 cm, Figure 9.3) between the two wetland pools. Average

water depths of all sampling locations were greatest in the winter (43 ± 23 cm) and lowest in the fall (19 ± 18 cm; Table B9.3). The discrete, manually-collected water depths shown in Figure 9.3 and Tables B9.2–B9.3 represent the water depths at the location where water samples were collected, which are not always representative of the deepest location within a wetland feature. Therefore, average water depths at the deepest pool location may at times be greater than reported given that access to the deepest point of some wetland pools is not always safely feasible.

Figure 9.3. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Average dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) concentrations and total phosphorus (TP) concentrations were lower at Great Miami River Downstream (0.171 and 0.283 mg P/L, respectively) than Great Miami River Upstream (0.214 and 0.331 mg P/L, respectively). Great Miami River Downstream at Barbie Park had DRP and TP concentrations (0.296 and 0.409 mg P/L, respectively) that were greater than both upstream and downstream locations, possibly indicating a source of phosphorus (P) input between the downstream location and downstream at Barbie Park (Table B9.4). Average North Pool and South Pool DRP and TP concentrations were lower than average Spring Creek and Great Miami River concentrations (Table B9.4, Figure 9.4).

Spring Creek had the highest average nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) and total nitrogen (TN) concentrations among all sampling locations (3.802 and 4.381 mg N/L, respectively; Table 9.1). Just like for DRP and TP, average NO_x and TN concentrations were lower at Great Miami River Downstream (2.782 and 3.784 mg N/L, respectively) than Great Miami River Upstream (2.871 and 3.811 mg N/L, respectively). However, unlike DRP and TP, NO_x and TN concentrations were also lower further downstream at Barbie Park (2.387 and 3.603 mg N/L, respectively; Table 9.1).

Soil Nutrient Status

Average Mehlich 3-extracted P (M3-P), iron (M3-Fe), and aluminum (M3-Al) concentrations are fairly consistent across the wetland soil sampling locations, except for M3-Al concentration at South Pool that is an order of magnitude lower than the other two locations (20.13 ± 28.5 mg Al/kg, Table B9.10). This low Al concentration results in a lower Soil Phosphate Storage Capacity (SPSC) value of 9.206 ± 10.9 mg P/kg, meaning there is less capacity for soils to sorb P in the South Pool compared to the North Pool and Connecting Channel (Table B9.10, Figure 9.5).

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

In 2024, data from existing water level loggers and a bathymetry survey completed by the Miami Conservancy District will support nutrient function assessment. A new sampling location downstream of the wetland (Great Miami River Downstream at Barbie Park) was added in 2023. Collecting more samples from this downstream location will help determine the nutrient reduction potential of the Project.

Non-Focal Projects: Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands (SPRC)

Figure 9.4. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Non-Focal Projects: Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands (SPRC)

Table 9.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Spring Creek	3.802 ± 1.9	25 (0)	0.45–7.23	0.005 ± 0	18 (8)	0–0.01	4.381 ± 2.1	25 (0)	0.96–7.9
02. North Pool	2.164 ± 1.3	32 (1)	0–4.76	0.016 ± 0	23 (6)	0–0.12	2.77 ± 1.5	32 (0)	0.45–6.59
03. Connecting Channel	2.123 ± 1	17 (0)	0.08–3.52	0.058 ± 0.2	15 (4)	0–0.59	3.027 ± 1.3	17 (0)	0.49–5.15
04. South Pool	0.949 ± 0.9	32 (2)	0–3.24	0.019 ± 0	23 (6)	0–0.13	1.94 ± 1.2	32 (0)	0.65–5.62
05. Great Miami River Downstream	2.782 ± 2	32 (1)	0–7.37	0.034 ± 0	23 (3)	0–0.17	3.784 ± 2.1	32 (0)	0.37–8.33
06. Great Miami River Upstream	2.871 ± 2	30 (0)	0.36–7.97	0.036 ± 0	21 (0)	0–0.09	3.811 ± 2.3	30 (0)	1.04–9.34
07. Great Miami River Downstream at Barbie Park	2.387 ± 1.9	12 (0)	0.41–5.73	0.058 ± 0.1	3 (0)	0.01–0.12	3.603 ± 2.3	12 (0)	1.24–7.92

Figure 9.5. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Additional Plots

Figure 9.6. Daily volume (gallons) of the South Pool (near the Great Miami River) at the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project calculated using bathymetry data and continuous water level measurements. The dashed line indicates inflow events when the Great Miami River breached the inflow notch and flowed into the wetland. Note that daily volume is represented in millions (M) of gallons.

Figure 9.7. Daily volume (gallons) of the North Pool (near Spring Creek) at the Springcreek Confluence Off-Channel Wetlands Project calculated using bathymetry data and continuous water level measurements. The dashed line indicates inflow events when Spring Creek breached the inflow notch and flowed into the wetland. Note that daily volume is represented in millions (M) of gallons.

Figure 9.8. Great Miami River streamflow from 9/1/2021 to 12/31/2023 obtained from USGS gage #03262700 watershed weighted to get discharge at the wetland. Blue indicates flow, and the black circles indicate sampling events. The dashed line is 5,529 CFS, above which storm flow water will enter the South Pool of the Wetland.

Figure 9.9. Spring Creek streamflow from 9/1/2021 to 12/31/23 obtained from USGS gage #03262700 watershed weighted to get discharge at the wetland. Blue indicates flow, and the black circles indicate sampling events. The dashed line is 204 CFS, above which storm flow water will enter the North Pool of the Wetland.

Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration (SRHE)

Project Overview

Crawford County | Sandusky River Watershed

Project size: 7 Acres

Partners: Crawford Park District

ODNR Description: “The Sandusky Headwaters Preserve is located in Crawford County just down from where Paramour Creek and Allen Run combine to form the Sandusky River. For this project, wetlands were restored on two adjacent agricultural fields totaling ~7-acres. Two wetland pools are fed by a small stream draining an agricultural field that travels through a forested hillside prior to splitting into the two pools. Prior to construction the small stream was a channelized ditch that bisected the fields and fed directly into the Sandusky River. There are also 6 depressions constructed in the eastern field to serve as vernal pool habitat. These combined efforts will improve water quality by reducing nutrient loading into the Sandusky River.”¹⁰

Management Considerations

Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration appears to be functioning as intended (as a flow-through wetland) and is storing nutrients. Prior to construction, upland agriculture runoff entered the channelized stream and flowed directly into the Sandusky River. The installation of this Project diverted the stream into two wetland pools thereby creating a buffer and allowing those nutrients to be stored or removed. Researchers anecdotally noticed that the East Wetland (Figure 10.1), including wet meadow and vernal pools, is more densely vegetated than the West Wetland and has a larger diversity of vegetation, likely resulting from more persistent inundation in the East compared to West wetland. Over time as the West Wetland establishes fully, similar vegetation densities might be seen.

Sampling Approach

Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland is a flow-through wetland consisting of two main wetland pools and a series of smaller vernal pools. The Project is split between the East and the West Wetland pools by a primary inflow stream (Figure 10.1). Flow from the primary inflow stream originates in a small agricultural field and flows down to the Project area through forested hillside. The primary inflow then splits between the East and West Wetlands, with slightly more flow going to the East Wetland inflow. The eastern portion of the site consists of one larger, densely vegetated wetland pool that drains into a large wet meadow before it drains to the Sandusky River. There are also a series of smaller vernal pools to the east of the wetland that rarely hold water. During high flow, water drains from the pool into the wet meadow and overflows a small berm to connect to the previous ditch channel that connects to the Sandusky

¹⁰ “Sandusky Headwaters Preserve Wetland and Habitat Restoration.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/sandusky-headwaters-preserve/>

River. The west wetland is a large open pool with less vegetation and a more defined outflow channel that disperses into a wet meadow. During ambient conditions the outflow does not typically have water, but during high flow events the outflow fills the wet meadow and overflows into a different small stream prior to flowing into the Sandusky River.

This is a non-focal Project; therefore, samples are collected seasonally and during the peak of two to three major storm events per year. Samples are collected from the primary inflow (before it splits), the East and West Wetlands, the East and West Outflows, and the vernal pools if water is present in the pool. During ambient conditions, the main pools and outflows are sampled in one location, but during high flow events they may be sampled in 2 locations depending on the location of the storm plume. The East Wetland main pool is a deep pool that retains water year-round even during drought, and the West Wetland will often be dry during the late summer and fall. The Sandusky River is also sampled adjacent to the Project.

Sampling Locations

- 01. Primary Inflow
- 02. East Wetland Inflow
- 03. East Wetland A
- 04. East Wetland B
- 05. East Outflow A
- 06. East Outflow B
- 07. West Wetland Inflow
- 08. West Wetland A
- 09. West Wetland B
- 10. West Outflow A
- 11. West Outflow B
- 12. Cow Pond
- 13. Sandusky River
- 14. Vernal Pool 1
- 15. Vernal Pool 2
- 16. Vernal Pool 3
- 17. Vernal Pool 4
- 18. Vernal Pool 5
- 19. Vernal Pool 6

Figure 10.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Sampling Location Water Depths

The East Wetland consistently had the deepest mean pool depths (44 and 55 cm at wetlands A and B, respectively) compared to the mean pool depths in the West Wetland (30 and 29 cm at wetlands A and B, respectively; Table B10.2). These depths can be attributed to both pool

construction and proportion of flow each wetland received during events. Vernal pools 1–5 were not measured for depth consistently and reported measurements were only collected when pools had water, therefore the vernal pools had less reported depth measurements than the East and West Wetlands. Vernal pool 4 was never measured for depth; vernal pool 3 contained water once and it was 39 cm, the deepest mean for all vernal pools (Table B10.2). Wetland mean pool depths were deepest in the winter (40 cm) and spring (35cm) months (Table B10.3, Figure 10.2). Winter and spring are when most of the storm and high flow events occur and when the water table is highest.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Total phosphorus (TP) concentration in the outflow of the East Wetland (East Outflow B: 0.103 mg P/L) was higher than both the Primary Inflow (before the stream splits; 0.091 mg P/L) and the East Wetland Inflow (0.065 mg P/L). However, East Wetland outflow had a lower dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) concentration (East Outflow B: 0.019 mg P/L) than both the East Wetland Inflow (0.029 mg P/L) and Primary Inflow (0.04 mg P/L; Table B10.4). The West Wetland functioned to retain TP and DRP. The TP and DRP concentrations at the West Wetland Outflow B (0.054 and 0 mg P/L, respectively) were lower than the Primary Inflow (0.091 and 0.04 mg P/L, respectively; Table B10.4). The Sandusky River consistently had higher average concentrations of TP and DRP compared to the wetland sampling locations, even the Primary Inflow (Table B10.4, Figure 10.3). Often there was no outflow of either wetland indicating all inflow P was retained, i.e., we only collected 3 samples from the wetland outflow in 2023 but had 11–12 samples from the wetland pools. It is important to note that these samples were primarily collected during ambient conditions and do not reflect retention during stormflow conditions.

Seasonally, winter had the greatest mean TP concentration (0.158 mg P/L) and fall had the greatest mean DRP concentration (0.053 mg P/L), while spring had the lowest TP and DRP concentrations (0.42 and 0.002 mg P/L, respectively; Table B10.5). High nutrient concentrations in the winter and fall can be attributed to high flow, rain events, and potential release from plant decomposition. However, the East Wetland Outflow B concentration are still lower than the Sandusky River (0.152 mg P/L).

Similar to phosphorus (P), the Sandusky River had the highest nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) and total nitrogen (TN) concentrations (1.948 and 2.68 mg N/L, respectively), notably higher than the small stream feeding the wetland pools (Primary Inflow = 0.87 and 1.267 mg N/L, respectively; Table 10.1). NO_x concentrations were higher than the Primary Inflow in East Wetland B and West Wetland B, but those were specifically collected during high flow events. East and West Wetland A both had NO_x concentrations lower than the Primary Inflow. West Outflow A had the greatest mean total ammonia (NH₃) concentration for the Project at 0.136 mg N/L (Table 10.1). Seasonally, winter had the highest NO_x (1.177 mg N/L) and TN (1.989 mg N/L) mean concentrations and fall had the highest mean NH₃ (0.056 mg N/L; Table B10.7). It is important

Non-Focal Projects: Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration (SRHE)

to note that West Wetland Outflow A was essentially a wetland pool during high flow events, so West Wetland Outflow B should be used to determine true outflow events.

Figure 10.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil pH levels were within a neutral range (6.69–7.54) for all sampling locations except for East Wetland A at 8.14 (Table B10.8). Soil conductivity was highly variable ranging from 19.2 to 719 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, and averaged 69.9 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at Vernal Pool 1 and 386 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at East Outflow A (Table B10.8). Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) results indicated that the Project had the ability to sorb phosphate (Table B10.10). The West Outflow A had the lowest SPSC value (65.5 mg P/kg), yet it was still positive indicating a moderate ability to sorb phosphate (Figure 10.4). Mehlich 3-extractable aluminum (M3-Al) and iron (M3-Fe) varied greatly across sampling locations and did not correlate to one another or Mehlich 3-extractable P levels (M3-P; Table B10.10).

East Outflow A had the greatest total nitrogen (TN) and total phosphorus (TP) soil concentration at 5289 mg N/kg and 1258 mg P/kg (Table B10.12). Overall, water-extractable nitrate (0.671 mg N/kg) and ammonia (10.17 mg N/kg) was higher than water-extractable phosphate (0.464 mg P/kg). While this Project has a high capacity to sorb phosphate, most of the available phosphate was found at the outflows indicating these locations might be the first to release P once the site reaches total P capacity (Table B10.12).

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

Over the coming year, researchers will be assessing continuous water level measurements along with water level of the incoming stream to calculate the volume of water stored at this Project. This may support a rough nutrient load reduction estimate associated with this wetland restoration.

Non-Focal Projects: Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration (SRHE)

Figure 10.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Non-Focal Projects: Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration (SRHE)

Table 10.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Primary Inflow	0.87 \pm 0.9	9 (0)	0–2.62	0.018 \pm 0	9 (2)	0–0.04	1.267 \pm 1	9 (0)	0.31–3.42
02. East Wetland Inflow	0.185 \pm 0.3	6 (0)	0–0.77	0.016 \pm 0	6 (0)	0–0.04	0.63 \pm 0.4	6 (0)	0.14–1.21
03. East Wetland A	0.559 \pm 0.8	12 (0)	0–2.39	0.041 \pm 0	12 (0)	0.01–0.17	1.552 \pm 1.3	12 (0)	0.28–4.27
04. East Wetland B	1.449 \pm 0.3	3 (0)	1.17–1.69	0.029 \pm 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.04	2.189 \pm 0.7	3 (0)	1.67–3.04
06. East Outflow B	0.076 \pm 0.1	2 (0)	0–0.15	0.015 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.02	0.817 \pm 0.3	2 (0)	0.6–1.03
07. West Wetland Inflow	0.145 \pm 0.2	2 (0)	0–0.29	0.055 \pm 0	2 (0)	0.03–0.08	1.72 \pm 1.7	2 (0)	0.52–2.92
08. West Wetland A	0.516 \pm 0.7	7 (0)	0–1.57	0.025 \pm 0	7 (0)	0–0.06	1.118 \pm 1	7 (0)	0.16–2.67
09. West Wetland B	0.805 \pm 0.7	4 (0)	0.01–1.63	0.022 \pm 0	4 (0)	0–0.06	1.65 \pm 0.8	4 (0)	0.5–2.38
10. West Outflow A	0.525 \pm 0.8	3 (0)	0.06–1.42	0.136 \pm 0.2	3 (0)	0.01–0.38	1.108 \pm 1	3 (0)	0.43–2.31
11. West Outflow B	0 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0	0.01 \pm 0	3 (0)	0–0.02	0.398 \pm 0.1	3 (0)	0.27–0.47
12. Cow Pond	0.032 \pm 0.1	4 (0)	0–0.13	0.098 \pm 0.1	4 (0)	0–0.18	0.935 \pm 0.5	4 (0)	0.27–1.5
13. Sandusky River	1.948 \pm 1.3	13 (0)	0.22–4.87	0.065 \pm 0.1	13 (0)	0–0.45	2.68 \pm 1.6	13 (0)	0.67–6.62
14. Vernal Pool 1	0.177 \pm 0.3	4 (0)	0–0.66	0.017 \pm 0	4 (0)	0–0.04	0.305 \pm 0.4	4 (0)	0.04–0.82

Non-Focal Projects: Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration (SRHE)

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
15. Vernal Pool 2	0.448 ± 0.3	2 (0)	0.24–0.66	0.019 ± 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.03	1.298 ± 0.7	2 (0)	0.78–1.81
16. Vernal Pool 3	0 ± NA	1 (0)	0–0	0.031 ± NA	1 (0)	0.03–0.03	1.05 ± NA	1 (0)	1.05–1.05
18. Vernal Pool 5	0 ± 0	2 (0)	0–0	0.028 ± 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.05	0.765 ± 0.4	2 (0)	0.46–1.07

Figure 10.4. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve Wetland & Habitat Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat (SUGB)

Project Overview

Putnam County

Project size: 6 Acres

Partner: Private Landowner

From ODNR: “Sugarcamp 7 is primarily a flow-through wetland that also functions as a floodplain wetland under abnormally high flows. It is located adjacent to the Blanchard River near the village of Ottawa and is bordered to the southwest by a small ditch that leads directly to the river. Prior to restoration, the project was an agricultural field and therefore the project remains surrounded by agriculture. The primary wetland pool is fed by surface runoff through a grassed waterway, tile drainage from the west, and drainage from a septic tank complex for ~7 households to the southeast of the project and drains directly to the Blanchard River.”¹¹

Management Considerations

Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat (hereafter Sugarcamp 7) is a unique H2Ohio wetland in that it treats both point source (septic tank) and nonpoint source (tile drain) inflows. This helps maintain a consistent water level and nutrient source in the main pool. Often the main pool outflow had no flow, therefore much of the nutrient input was stored and not exported. More data collection should help researchers better quantify the long-term nature of that storage. The vernal pool and the hummock and hollow pools are variable in their water storage. Some hummock and hollow pools have never contained water, some have water seasonally, and some will flood with the river. Researchers have not had the opportunity to capture an event where the Blanchard River floods into the Project, but we will watch to see if higher flows flood the Project in future years.

Sampling Approach

This Project is both a flow-through and floodplain wetland. It consists of one large main flow-through wetland along with a larger vernal pool and a multitude of small hummock and hollow pools (HH pools, Figure 11.1). The entire Project area will flood under flood warning conditions based on the U.S. Geological Survey gage in Ottawa, OH (~6,000 cubic feet per second, or CFS), which has not occurred since May 11, 2021. Under high-flow conditions (~3,000 CFS), the mouth of the stream to the river will overflow into the HH pool habitat. In the main pool, the tile drain and septic inputs are typically submerged under the pool water level and the grassed waterway simply overflows into the pool. The outflow is a defined channel where researchers have a continuously logging water level sensor. The main pool holds water year-round while select HH pools and the larger vernal pool contain water only after major rain events.

¹¹ “Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/blanchard-river-floodplain-wetland-restoration/>

This Project is a non-Focal Project; therefore, the goal is to sample seasonally and during the peak of one to two major storm events per year. Samples are collected from the main pool inflows, the middle of the main pool to allow for mixing, and the outflow (Figure 11.1). The HH pools and vernal pool are sampled if sufficient water is present, which is not common. There are over 50 HH pools on the property, so instead of sampling every pool that has water, researchers randomly select five pools if water is present to sample. Three storm events (9/21/22, 2/24/23, 8/24/23) and two ambient conditions (12/9/22, 4/18/23) have been captured since sampling started in September 2022.

Figure 11.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point. HH = Hummock and Hollow.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Pool depths across all sampling locations at Sugarcamp 7 ranged from 0 cm to 79 cm. The deepest locations were the main pool and the hummock/hollow pools (Figure 11.2). Due to accessibility constraints, the Blanchard River was sampled from the river bank and the measured depths were thus not representative of the river's deepest points (Table 11.2). In addition, many of the hummock and hollow pools were dry through much of the year and averaged far lower depths. Depth notably increased during storm events in the hummock and hollow pools and main

pool (Figure 11.2). In addition, researchers only had a measurable depth in the outflow during storm conditions and the grassed waterway during one storm event. The septic and tile inflows were sometimes submerged, so the depth measured at those locations often reflected the main pool depth at the edge rather than depth of water in the tile or septic pipes.

Figure 11.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Total phosphorus (TP) and dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) concentrations overall were higher in storm conditions compared to ambient conditions (Table 11.3). Ambient TP concentrations were still fairly elevated compared to other wetlands (> 0.15 mg/L), but with lower DRP concentrations, much of that phosphorus (P) was likely particulate bound or in organic form. Measurements of inflow concentrations during storms tended to be lower in TP and DRP concentrations compared to the main pool and the outflow (Table 11.3). However, this probably simply reflects that the researchers missed the storm event inflow and captured that event as it was exiting the main pool. It is well known that surface runoff and tile drain flow respond incredibly rapidly to storm events (over the span of a day or two) and researchers would have had to be out there shortly after the event to truly capture the input. More storm event sampling of water volume and water concentration is needed to fully understand the capacity of the main wetland pool to filter inputs to the river.

Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x) and total nitrogen (TN) concentrations were also higher in storm conditions compared to ambient (Table 11.4). Interestingly, NO_x concentrations were a small portion of TN during ambient conditions (~14–22%), but a much higher proportion during storm conditions (62–69%, Table 11.4). As with P, NO_x and TN concentrations were slightly higher in the outflow than the main pool and inflows, but that may be because peak inflow was missed and only captured by the time it reached the outflow. Total ammonia (NH₃) concentrations were low across most sampling locations (Table 11.4) and were highest in the one sample collected from the grassed waterway inflow in September 2022.

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil samples were collected once in 2023 from three locations in the main pool at Sugarcamp 7: shallow pool water, the edge of the pool where the soil was dry but is sometimes inundated, and in the middle of the pool or “open”. Soil pH was slightly above neutral and ranged from 7.1–7.7 with the highest pH observed at the edge location. Soil conductivity was fairly high compared to other H2Ohio wetland soils and ranged from 3527–5199 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Average Mehlich 3-extractable P (M3-P), iron (M3-Fe), and aluminum (M3-Al) were higher in the open water (29.4 mg P/kg, 1002 mg Fe/kg, 1071 mg Al/kg) compared to the shallow water or edge (21.6–28.4 mg P/kg, 317–643 mg Fe/kg, 644–839 mg Al/kg). The Soil Phosphate Storage Capacity (SPSC) was moderately positive (70–149 mg P/kg) indicating the soils have a high capacity to sorb P.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

Monitoring at this site can be challenging as inflows are frequently submerged below the main pool surface and the hummock and hollow pools cannot all be monitored due to its large abundance. Researchers have installed continuous water level loggers at the main pool and outflow and are looking forward to translating that information into water storage and possible load reduction estimates over the coming year.

Figure 11.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table 11.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. HH Pool 1	0.013 ± 0	3 (0)	0–0.04	0.016 ± 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.02	1.353 ± 0.4	3 (0)	0.9–1.7
02. HH Pool 2	0.053 ± 0.1	3 (0)	0–0.16	0.017 ± 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.02	2.257 ± 1.3	3 (0)	0.75–3.17
03. HH Pool 3	1.76 ± 3	4 (0)	0–6.26	0.02 ± 0	4 (0)	0.01–0.03	2.93 ± 2.9	4 (0)	0.46–7.15
04. HH Pool 4	0.7 ± 1.1	3 (0)	0–2	0.035 ± 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.07	1.867 ± 1.3	3 (0)	0.52–3.01
05. HH Pool 5	0.065 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0–0.13	0.023 ± 0	2 (0)	0.02–0.03	1.18 ± 0.8	2 (0)	0.58–1.78
06. HH Pool 6	0.105 ± 0.1	2 (0)	0–0.21	0.018 ± 0	2 (0)	0.01–0.02	1.18 ± 0.8	2 (0)	0.64–1.72
07. Outflow	2.702 ± 1.4	3 (0)	1.47–4.15	0.098 ± 0.1	3 (0)	0.02–0.18	5.468 ± 2.7	3 (0)	2.95–8.31
08. Main Pool	2.032 ± 2	6 (0)	0.02–4.84	0.037 ± 0	6 (0)	0.01–0.11	3.908 ± 2.6	6 (0)	1.54–7.85
09. Grass Inflow	2.79 ± NA	1 (0)	2.79–2.79	0.119 ± NA	1 (0)	0.12–0.12	5.74 ± NA	1 (0)	5.74–5.74
10. Tile Inflow	2.4 ± NA	1 (0)	2.4–2.4	0.025 ± NA	1 (0)	0.03–0.03	5.08 ± NA	1 (0)	5.08–5.08
11. Septic Inflow	0.908 ± 1.6	3 (0)	0–2.72	0.027 ± 0	3 (0)	0.02–0.04	2.767 ± 2.4	3 (0)	0.9–5.45
12. Inflow 2	4.49 ± NA	1 (0)	4.49–4.49	0.049 ± NA	1 (0)	0.05–0.05	6.47 ± NA	1 (0)	6.47–6.47

Table 11.2. Summarized discrete water depth measurements collected at the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project organized by ambient and storm conditions (identified using turbidity measurements in the field as a proxy to storm events). Values are reported as mean along with the number of summarized observations. n.d. = not determined.

Sampling Location	Ambient Conditions		Storm Conditions	
	Water Depth (cm)	Sample Size	Water Depth (cm)	Sample Size
HH Pools	25.4	10	52.3	7
Vernal Pool	19	2	n.d.	0
Main Pool	39.5	2	47.7	3
Septic Inflow	n.d.	0	8.5	2
Tile Inflow	n.d.	0	5	2
Grass Inflow	n.d.	0	2	1
Outflow	n.d.	0	25	2
River	n.d.	0	22.5	2

Table 11.3. Summarized surface water concentrations of total (TP) and dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) collected at the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project organized by ambient and storm conditions (identified using turbidity measurements in the field as a proxy to storm events). Values are reported as means. n.d. = not determined.

Sampling Location	Ambient Conditions		Storm Conditions	
	TP (mg P/L)	DRP (mg P/L)	TP (mg P/L)	DRP (mg P/L)
HH Pools	0.22	0.02	0.81	0.28
Vernal Pool	0.2	0.01	n.d.	n.d.
Main Pool	0.17	0	0.7	0.13
Septic Inflow	n.d.	n.d.	0.49	0.04
Tile Inflow	n.d.	n.d.	0.36	0.11
Grass Inflow	n.d.	n.d.	0.39	0.06
Outflow	n.d.	n.d.	0.78	0.1
River	n.d.	n.d.	0.56	0.16

Non-Focal Projects: Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat (SUGB)

Table 11.4. Summarized surface water concentrations of nitrate+nitrite, total ammonia, and total nitrogen (TN) collected at the Sugarcamp 7 Blanchard Habitat Project organized by ambient and storm conditions (identified using turbidity measurements in the field as a proxy to storm events). Values are reported as means. n.d. = not determined.

Sampling Location	Ambient Conditions			Storm Conditions		
	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)	Total Ammonia (mg N/L)	TN (mg N/L)	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)	Total Ammonia (mg N/L)	TN (mg N/L)
HH Pools	0.33	0.02	1.48	3.2	0.02	4.62
Vernal Pool	0	0.02	0.93	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
Main Pool	0.24	0.03	1.65	3.76	0.05	6.06
Septic Inflow	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	1.36	0.03	3.7
Tile Inflow	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	1.91	0.05	3.97
Grass Inflow	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	2.79	0.12	5.74
Outflow	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	3.32	0.06	6.73
River	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	2.13	0.1	4.25

Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland (TIPC)

Project Overview

Miami County

Project Size: 18.3 acres

Partners: City of Tipp City

ODNR Description: “This project restored off-channel habitat along the Great Miami River near the confluence of Honey Creek in Tipp City, Ohio. The area includes restored wetlands, a basin that is approximately 9.5 acres, and connections to the river made after the basin was revegetated. Off-channel wetlands like this provide nutrient-reduction benefits to the nearby river as well as reducing peak streamflow during runoff events.”¹²

Management Considerations

Lowering the inflow notch would facilitate more opportunity for additional water to enter this floodplain wetland. A water control structure placed on the downstream side of the wetland at the inflow notch would allow for more active management by forcing longer periods of water storage after flooding events, but would require active surveillance.

Sampling Approach

Construction of the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland was completed in 2022. Water from the Great Miami River enters a large riparian floodplain through an inflow notch when the river reaches a discharge of 2,623 cubic feet per second (CFS). Water samples are collected monthly and soil samples are collected annually from the Great Miami River upstream, downstream, and two locations in the floodplain to assess nutrient load reduction (Figure 12.1). A water level logger (HOBO[®] Onset) was placed in the wetland pool to determine changes in pool volume over time.

¹² “Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/tipp-city-off-channel/>

Sampling Locations

- 01. Great Miami River (upstream)
- 02. Wetland Inflow
- 03. Mid Wetland (near HOB0)
- 04. Great Miami River (downstream)

Figure 12.1 Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Manually measured water depths were greatest on average at the Great Miami River Downstream sampling location (60 ± 25 cm) and lowest at the Wetland Inflow (31 ± 16 cm) amongst all sampling locations (Table B12.2, Figure 12.2). Average water depths across all sampling locations were greatest in the winter (57 ± 28 cm) when most of the high discharge/inflow events occur (Table B12.3). Water depths presented in Tables B12.2 and B12.3 and Figure 12.2 represent the water depths from where the water sample was collected, and do not always represent the water depth at the deepest location within a given wetland feature.

Figure 12.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Average dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) concentrations in the Great Miami River were lower downstream from the wetland. On average, DRP and TP concentrations were 43% and 36% lower downstream compared to upstream (Table B12.4, Figure 12.3). On average, nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) and total nitrogen (TN) concentrations were 20% lower downstream from the wetland than upstream (Table 12.1). Average dissolved and total nutrients were lower in the wetland than the Great Miami River, which is indicative of nutrient processing inside the wetland (Table 12.1, Table B12.4).

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil data not available for the 2023 Annual Report.

Nutrient Load Calculation

Results

From December 2022 to December 2023, dissolved and total nitrogen and phosphorus were retained by the wetland and prevented from moving downstream in the Great Miami River. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x) and total nitrogen (TN) loads were reduced by 1645 and 1444 lbs of N, respectively. Greater reduced loads of dissolved nutrients than total nutrients suggest that the rate at which dissolved nutrients are processed inside the wetland is greater relative to processing of particulate nutrients. Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) loads were reduced by 69.7 and 108 lbs of P, respectively. Seasonally, greatest TP, NO_x, and TN loads were reduced in the winter corresponding with large inflow events from the Great Miami River (Figure 12.4).

Volume

To calculate daily changes in the volume of water in the Tipp City wetland, researchers combined bathymetric survey data with continuously monitored (every 30 minutes) sensor-measured surface water depths (HOBO). Water depths measured every 30 minutes are averaged to daily water depth calculations. Daily pool volume is then calculated using data from a recent bathymetry survey completed by Donnie Knight of U.S. Fish & Wildlife; where volume of water (Figure 12.6) is related back to area with acreage corresponding to the total area at a given corresponding depth at the time of survey. An acre-foot is a unit of water volume equivalent to the volume of water that would cover an acre of land to about 1 ft deep, 1 acre-foot is approximately equal to 326,000 gallons of water. Thus, daily volume is calculated using the equation: $\text{volume} = 326,000 \text{ gallons} \times \text{depth (ft)} \times \text{acres}$ where depth acres is the area that corresponds or exists at a given water depth. Change in daily pool volume is calculated by subtracting the previous day's pool volume from the current pool volume. All the positive changes in pool volume (inflows) were added together over a season to obtain total seasonal inflows. This method accounts for the fact that water can enter the site via both the surface water

connection (the inflow notch) as well as via subsurface flow through the sandy, permeable soils that separate the river from the wetland (the hyporheic zone).

Concentration

Two sampling locations within the Project (Wetland Inflow and Mid Wetland) were averaged to obtain an average “Wetland” nutrient concentration. Seasonal average nutrient concentrations were calculated for the Great Miami River Upstream and “Wetland”. Seasons were defined as Winter Dec. 15 to March 14, Spring March 15 to June 14, Summer June 15 to Sept. 14, and Fall Sept. 15 to Dec. 14, roughly capturing different flow pattern regimes throughout the year. Differences between the Great Miami River Upstream and Wetland were calculated and multiplied by total inflows over the season to determine seasonal nutrient load reduced.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

Continuing data collection could greatly improve our estimates of wetland efficacy. Specifically, monitoring during more storm events would improve estimates and understanding of functionality at higher flows.

Non-Focal Projects: Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland (TIPC)

Figure 12.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table 12.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Great Miami River (upstream)	2.783 ± 1.9	14 (0)	0.65–6.02	0.09 ± 0.1	6 (0)	0.01–0.29	3.503 ± 1.9	14 (0)	1.48–7.39
02. Wetland Inflow	0.567 ± 0.8	16 (6)	0–2.77	0.005 ± 0	6 (2)	0–0.01	1.514 ± 1.4	16 (0)	0.17–5.24
03. Mid Wetland (near HOB0)	0.552 ± 0.9	16 (7)	0–2.69	0.005 ± 0	6 (2)	0–0.01	1.691 ± 1.3	16 (0)	0.52–4.73
04. Great Miami River (downstream)	2.216 ± 1.3	16 (1)	0–4.24	0.061 ± 0.1	6 (0)	0.01–0.23	2.8 ± 1.1	16 (0)	1.25–5.58

Additional Plots

Figure 12.4. Daily volume (gallons) of the Mid Wetland Pool at the Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland Project calculated using bathymetry data and continuous water level measurements. Red arrows and points indicate dates of inflow events when the Great Miami River breached the inflow notch and flowed into the wetland. Note that daily volume is represented in millions (M) of gallons.

Figure 12.5. Great Miami River streamflow from 12/1/2022 to 12/1/2023 from USGS gage #03262700 watershed weighted to get discharge at the wetland. Blue indicates flow, and the black circles indicate sampling events. The dashed line is 2,623 CFS, above which storm flow water will enter Tipp City Off-Channel Wetland.

Figure 12.6. Bathymetry survey completed by Donnie Knight of US Fish & Wildlife in February of 2023. Water depths were used to calculate volume of water at various water depths.

Trumbull Creek (TRUC)

Project Overview

Ashtabula County

Project Size: 30 Acres

Partner: Stream and Wetlands Foundation

ODNR Description: “This Project will permanently remove a 30-acre agricultural field, a large source of sediment and nutrient loading, keeping nitrogen and phosphorus from the Grand River watershed and Lake Erie. Once completed in December 2021, provided for the restoration of approximately 20 acres of forested wetlands, 5 acres of emergent marsh, and 6 acres of upland forest. These actions will slow the flow of water across the landscape, restoring a more natural runoff after storms while providing important habitat for wildlife, recreation, and educational opportunities.”¹³

Management Considerations

The Trumbull Creek Project sits at a watershed divide between Mill Creek (HUC 041100040602) and Bronson Creek (HUC 041100040502) and thus does not receive major nutrient loading from any upstream or upslope areas. As such, a primary management concern is whether legacies of past agricultural land use will lead to net phosphorus (P) release from soils after conversion to wetland. Early observations indicate that soils at the Trumbull Creek Project are not releasing P and P is not being exported from the project to downstream systems. However, information about connectivity is critical to elucidate net nutrient retention. Accurate and prompt reporting of water level management actions (e.g., via Survey123 or email) at the Project, specifically changes to the outflow water control structure (WCS), will allow researchers to generate actionable data to inform management actions and derive better estimates of nutrient retention. The water level control structure is the primary outflow for the water at this site and such tracking will allow researchers to know when water is leaving the Project and at what rate.

Sampling Approach

The Trumbull Creek Project has distinct lowland areas consisting of regularly inundated pools, and upland areas consisting of hummock and hollow microtopography. This Project is an inland wetland that sits on a watershed divide between Mill Creek and Bronson Creek. There is no direct surface water inflow, and the groundwater interactions are predicted to be minimal given the clay-dominated soil. The primary hydrologic input is precipitation, which collects in a series of hollow pools and lowland borrow pools (named because of the soil borrowed from that location to build the barrier around the Project; Figure 13.1). The hydrologic outflow is at a water level control structure (AgriDrain), which contains boards that can be added or removed to hold or remove water from the wetland. Sampling has primarily been designed to characterize

¹³ “Trumbull Creek Wetlands Restoration Project.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/trumbull-creek-wetlands-restoration-project/>

the variability of water and soil across the Project (Figure 13.2), and to collect samples that inform an estimate of nutrient storage over time, rather than comparing the difference between water entering and leaving the site. Communication with the wetland managers is essential for altering the sampling approach if and when the water level management changes.

Figure 13.1. Image displaying the hummock/hollow restoration technique used in the restoration of the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project. A small skid-steer with a bucket was used to push earthen mounds into hummocks, leaving behind hollows left to fill in with water (left, February 2022). The summer following construction saw immense vegetation growth at the Project (right, June 2022).

Sampling Locations

- 01. Hummock Pool
- 02. Borrow Pool 1
- 03. Borrow Pool 2
- 04. WCS
- 05. Outflow

Figure 13.2. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Since its construction in 2021, the outflow water level control structure at the Trumbull Creek Project has not been altered, meaning the height of the control structure has remained the same and water only flows out of the Project (through the structure) after large precipitation events. The topography of the Trumbull Creek Project was designed so that water enters the site via precipitation and slowly moves around hummocks and through hollows until it reaches larger pools (i.e., Borrow Pools). Discrete water depths were variable across the sampling locations of the Project and are dependent on how precipitation has contributed to the Project. The Hummock Pool sampling location has a smaller area compared to the Borrow Pools and the pool near the WCS, but its water depth reached similar magnitudes to Borrow Pools throughout the year (18–43 cm; Figure 13.3, Table B13.2). Due to the high influence of precipitation events on water level at the Trumbull Creek Project, discrete water depths measured during water sampling events may not be the optimal approach to track water level at this Project.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Fluctuations in surface water dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) throughout the year at the water control structure sampling location (WCS) may be associated with inundation and a dilution effect when precipitation increases wetland water levels (Table B13.5, Figure 13.4). In the summer, when water levels are lower, we saw increased DRP concentrations (0.012 mg P/L), whereas in the spring, with high water levels, there were lower concentrations of DRP (0.006 mg P/L). The observed patterns in DRP concentration do not reflect expectations based on theory associated with shifting redox processes as we would expect inundation to lower redox potential and result in increased release of P from reduced iron oxides. More sampling in extremes of water levels may allow for more detailed conclusions about the observed patterns. The Outflow sampling location at the Trumbull Creek Project was only able to be sampled once in 2023, however during that period, DRP and total phosphorus (TP) concentrations were similar or lower at the Outflow compared to all other sampling points (0.006 and 0.018 mg P/L, respectively).

Total ammonia (NH₃) concentrations appeared to be stable throughout the seasons across all sampling locations (0.018–0.025 mg N/L; Table B13.7). There was a clear increase in nitrate+nitrite (NO_x) concentrations in the fall at the Project (0.014 vs. 0.002–0.003 mg N/L; Table B13.7). This could be attributed to senescence of vegetation material in and around the pools and subsequent leaching of nitrogen (N) into the water.

Figure 13.3. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Non-Focal Projects: Trumbull Creek (TRUC)

Figure 13.4. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Table 13.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Trumbull Creek H2Ohio Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NOx) and total ammonia (NH₃) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Hummock Pool	0.008 ± 0	5 (1)	0–0.01	0.029 ± 0	5 (0)	0.01–0.06
02. Borrow Pool 1	0.012 ± 0	4 (1)	0–0.04	0.024 ± 0	4 (0)	0.01–0.03
03. Borrow Pool 2	0.005 ± 0	4 (0)	0–0.01	0.01 ± 0	4 (0)	0.01–0.01
04. WCS	0.005 ± 0	7 (2)	0–0.01	0.017 ± 0	7 (0)	0.01–0.02
05. Outflow	0.036 ± NA	1 (0)	0.04–0.04	0.042 ± NA	1 (0)	0.04–0.04

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil data not available for 2023 Annual Report.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

The Trumbull Creek Project is constructed in a way that makes sampling for nutrient budget purposes simple: there is no direct inflow and only one direct outflow. In the future, close monitoring of water level at the outflow (via staff gauge and water level sensor) will be important to determine when water is leaving the project.

Researchers have only successfully collected one outflow water sample since the start of monitoring (2022) because of the transient nature of flow in response to precipitation events at this Project. This was also the only time in which researchers have observed water actively flowing through the outflow water control structure. As more data is collected at the outflow, especially during high flow events, researchers will be able to better characterize the contribution of N and P to the surrounding landscape of the Trumbull Creek Project. A staff gauge installed in 2023 will provide more accurate water level monitoring, particularly when paired with a continuously logging water level sensor to be deployed in 2024. Researchers currently have accurate elevation and LiDAR data that can be used to model hydrology throughout the site with the accurate water level data collected using the staff gauge.

Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration (VANO)

Project Overview

Henry County | Maumee State Forest Addition

Project Size: 31 Acres

Partners: ODNR Division of Forestry

ODNR Description: “This project includes both wetland creation and forest restoration on a former agricultural field. The implemented practices will naturally capture phosphorus-laden runoff to reduce the amount of nutrients entering agricultural ditches and slow flow into nearby waterways. Tree species to be planted include white oak, red oak, black oak, black cherry, black walnut, hickory, and, if available, American chestnut and butternut.”¹⁴

Management Considerations

All pools at the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project (hereafter Van Order) appear to be functioning as intended by holding water during times of wetter weather but becoming dry during drier weather. Since construction was completed, the pools have been dry throughout much of the year (Figure 14.1). This is not surprising since most of this Project has soil with very high sand content, which drains water more rapidly than other soil types.

Sampling Approach

Construction at this Project was completed in 2021 and routine monitoring began soon after construction was complete in December 2021. Eight wetland pools were excavated to function primarily as geographically isolated wetlands (Figure 14.2) receiving water from surface runoff within the Project. An agricultural ditch intersects with the southern end of this Project, but it is unclear whether that ditch ever floods and overflows into wetland pools. Therefore, researchers sample the ditch and each wetland pool to monitor any unnoted hydrologic connection, given they only visit this Project about three times per year. All wetland pools are sampled individually about once per season (if water is present) and soil samples are collected once per year.

¹⁴ “Van Order Wetland and Forest Restoration.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/van-order-wetland-and-forest-restoration/>

Non-Focal Projects: Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration (VANO)

Figure 14.1. Looking south across Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. This Project's exceptionally sandy soil means it doesn't hold onto water for long, as seen during spring, summer, and fall 2023. Left: November 17, 2022. Right: May 5, 2023. (Genna Hunt)

Sampling Locations

- 01. Wetland Pool 1
- 02. Wetland Pool 2
- 03. Wetland Pool 3
- 04. Wetland Pool 4
- 05. Wetland Pool 5
- 06. Wetland Pool 6
- 07. Wetland Pool 7
- 08. Wetland Pool 8
- 09. South Ditch

Figure 14.2. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Sampling Location Water Depths

All pools at Van Order tended to be roughly comparable in depth (4–19 cm, on average). Wetland Pool 3 often had on average the deepest water (19 ± 18 cm), and the shallowest pools tended to be Pools 2 and 4 (5 ± 11 and 4 ± 9 cm, respectively; Table B14.2, Figure 14.3). The wetland pools at this Project experienced seasonal inundation. They filled with water during periods of heavy rain (i.e., winter and spring since the Project was constructed), then became dry through the summer and fall (Table B14.3). During four sampling trips in 2023 and five in 2022, researchers did not observe surface water connection between the South Ditch and the southern pools of this Project. Water depth measurements were generally taken at surface water sampling locations within pools, not always at the deepest point within pools.

Figure 14.3. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The

boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Average dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) concentrations were consistent across wetland pools (0–0.05 and 0.1–0.4 mg P/L, respectively; Table B14.4).

Summer had the highest mean TP concentrations overall (0.35 mg P/L; Table B14.5).

Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃), and total nitrogen (TN) were on average low in all wetland pools (0.1–0.75, 0–0.05, and 0.4–3 mg N/L, respectively; Table 14.1). The South Ditch tended to have higher NO_x, NH₃, and TN concentrations as expected for agricultural drainage relative to wetland water (Table 14.1).

Soil Nutrient Status

Mehlich 3-extracted phosphorus (M3-P) was less than 50 mg P/kg in all but Wetland Pool 4 (65 mg P/kg), which suggests that this former farm field was agronomically managed and excess fertilizer had not been applied (Table B14.10). Soil Phosphate Storage Capacity (SPSC) was 29–76 mg P/kg (Table B14.10), indicating good soil capacity to capture phosphorus (P). Water-extractable phosphate (H₂O-PO₄) was variable (0–0.65 mg P/kg) but overall was relatively low compared to soils collected from other H2Ohio Projects (Table B14.12). Water-extractable ammonia (H₂O-NH₄) was negligible (0–1.8 mg N/kg), and water-extractable nitrate (H₂O-NO₃) was low to moderate (3–10 mg N/kg) in wetland pools but high in the South Ditch (32 mg N/kg), as expected for agricultural drainage (Table B14.12). Average TP and TN concentrations in soils were typical for former agricultural fields, ranging between 130–400 mg P/kg for TP and 240–1000 mg N/kg for TN.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

In the coming year, we plan to install three water level loggers at this Project. These will support continuous collection of water level data and inform estimates of total input and output water volumes. Specifically, if we sensors high water level following heavy rain (typically late winter and early spring) and that will help to determine the degree of connection or lack thereof between the South Ditch and the southern portions of the Project. If a water level sensor can be installed at least in Pool 8 and ideally also in the South Ditch, we will assess the floodplain function in that area of the Project..

Non-Focal Projects: Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration (VANO)

Figure 14.4. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Non-Focal Projects: Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration (VANO)

Table 14.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Wetland Pool 1	0.426 ± 0.7	6 (0)	0.03–1.86	0.024 ± 0.1	6 (5)	0–0.14	3.019 ± 4.2	6 (0)	0.11–9.64
02. Wetland Pool 2	0.229 ± 0.3	4 (0)	0.05–0.71	0.037 ± 0.1	4 (2)	0–0.12	0.73 ± 0.7	4 (0)	0.09–1.75
03. Wetland Pool 3	0.659 ± 1.1	6 (0)	0.01–2.95	0.047 ± 0.1	6 (3)	0–0.13	2.244 ± 3.6	6 (0)	0.18–9.37
04. Wetland Pool 4	0.159 ± 0.2	3 (0)	0.05–0.37	0.007 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.02	0.863 ± 0.3	3 (0)	0.55–1.19
05. Wetland Pool 5	0.135 ± 0.2	4 (0)	0.01–0.4	0.01 ± 0	4 (3)	0–0.04	0.518 ± 0.5	4 (0)	0.11–1.25
06. Wetland Pool 6	0.745 ± 1.6	6 (1)	0–3.99	0.013 ± 0	6 (5)	0–0.08	2.157 ± 3.6	6 (0)	0.18–9.46
07. Wetland Pool 7	0.158 ± 0.1	5 (1)	0–0.33	0.003 ± 0	5 (4)	0–0.01	0.794 ± 0.6	4 (0)	0.26–1.68
08. Wetland Pool 8	0.091 ± 0.1	7 (0)	0.01–0.3	0 ± 0	7 (7)	0–0	0.421 ± 0.1	7 (0)	0.24–0.52
09. South Ditch	2.269 ± 1.8	2 (0)	1.02–3.52	0.018 ± 0	2 (1)	0–0.04	3.015 ± 1.9	2 (0)	1.69–4.34

Figure 14.5. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Van Order Wetland & Forest Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration (WALC)

Project Overview

Franklin County | Walnut Creek Watershed | Inland Central Ohio

Project Size: 17 Acres

Partner: Columbus and Franklin County Metro Parks

ODNR Description: “The Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project will add a 15-acre treatment train, or a series of wetlands, to the frequently flooded land near Walnut Creek. The project will receive, treat, and temporarily retain water from within the stream. The wetland will filter nutrients while also creating a functioning riparian ecosystem that will provide habitat for various amphibian, insect, and aquatic species. This new wetland treatment system will be viewable from a new walking trail that connect visitors to Walnut Woods Metro Park.”¹⁵

Management Considerations

For 2023, it appears there were approximately six to eight inflow periods (i.e., Walnut Creek flowed into the wetland during high flow events). More ways to bring water from Walnut Creek into the Project include lowering the elevation of the inflow notch and/or using a pump at the inflow notch. Invasive species control is something to be considered and prioritized for a management consideration, as *Phragmites* is quite prevalent in the Columbus area. In 2023, researchers observed long periods during which wetland soils were minimally inundated. If soils were inundated for longer periods of time, conditions may develop to promote soil characteristics that enhance nutrient removal.

Sampling Approach

Construction of the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project (hereafter Walnut Creek Project) was completed in 2023 and routine monitoring began in 2023. Water from Walnut Creek enters the wetland via an overflow notch when the creek reaches a certain water level/discharge (approximately 10.5 feet elevation per the USGS Ashville Station Water Level). At the inflow and outflow, there are deep settling pools to allow for the settling of particulate matter. The two settling pools are connected by a stretch of hummocks and hollows which receive water when the inflow settling pool is full. The water depth in the wetland pool and the outflow to Walnut Creek are controlled using two water control structures on the outflow pool. Water samples are collected monthly and soil samples are collected annually from Walnut Creek upstream, downstream, and three locations throughout the wetland to understand nutrient concentration at each wetland feature (Figure 15.1). Water level is continuously monitored at the outflow water level control structure (AgriDrain) using a sensor (Onset HOBO[®]) and the data is used to calculate outflow discharge using a flow over flat weir equation.

¹⁵ “Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/walnut-creek-treatment-wetland-restoration/>

- Sampling Locations**
- 01. Walnut Creek Inflow
 - 02. Early Wetland
 - 03. Mid Wetland
 - 04. Late Wetland
 - 05. Walnut Creek Outflow

Figure 15.1. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Sampling Location Water Depths

Average manually measured water depths were greatest for Walnut Creek Outflow (73 ± 36 cm) among all sampling locations (Table B15.2). Mid Wetland (hummocks and hollows) had an average water depth of 0 cm, meaning no water had been present in this area while collecting samples (Figure 15.2, Table B15.2). Water depths presented in Tables B15.2 and B15.3 and Figure 15.2 represent the water depths from where the water sample was collected, and do not always represent the water depth at the deepest location within a given wetland feature.

Figure 15.2. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Average dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) and total phosphorus (TP) concentrations in the Wetland (locations 2–4 in Figure 15.1) were much lower than in Walnut Creek (Figure 15.3,

Table B15.4). Walnut Creek Outflow (downstream; 0.197 mg P/L) had greater average DRP concentrations than Walnut Creek Inflow (upstream; 0.153 mg P/L). Average DRP and TP concentrations were greatest in the fall at 0.182 and 0.325 mg P/L, respectively (Table B15.5).

Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x) concentrations were on average lower in the Wetland (locations 2–4 in Figure 15.1) than in Walnut Creek (Table 15.1). However, NO_x concentration in Walnut Creek Outflow (downstream; 2.108 mg N/L) was marginally greater than Walnut Creek Inflow (upstream; 2.01 mg N/L). Average total nitrogen (TN) concentrations inside the Wetland were similar to Walnut Creek Inflow and Walnut Creek Outflow concentrations (Table 15.1). NO_x and TN concentrations were greatest in the summer at 1.8 and 3.5 mg N/L, respectively (Table B15.7).

Soil Nutrient Status

Soil data not available for the 2023 Annual Report.

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

The Walnut Creek Project will continue to be monitored to provide more information on the nutrient load reduction potential. A priority in 2024 will be event sampling (i.e., during and post storms) to capture upstream Walnut Creek flowing into the wetland and the wetland outflowing into downstream Walnut Creek. Researchers plan to test use of a trail camera at the inflow notch to help determine the exact discharge (as per the nearby USGS sensor on Walnut Creek) at which Walnut Creek flows into the wetland. If the trail camera detection of water level is effective, this approach may be applied in the future at additional H2Ohio Projects for monitoring, where appropriate.

It should be noted that majority of the downstream water samples (i.e., from Walnut Creek Outflow sampling location) were collected when the wetland was not outflowing into Walnut Creek. The nutrient concentrations at Walnut Creek Outflow could potentially be lower when the wetland is outflowing into the creek. If more samples are collected during outflow events, the potential nutrient load reduction for the Project can be more reliably determined.

Non-Focal Projects: Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration (WALC)

Figure 15.3. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Non-Focal Projects: Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration (WALC)

Table 15.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Walnut Creek Inflow	2.01 ± 0.9	8 (0)	1.36–4.09	0.014 ± 0	3 (0)	0.01–0.02	2.865 ± 1.1	8 (0)	1.9–4.78
02. Early Wetland	0.736 ± 1.6	6 (3)	0–3.92	0.095 ± NA	1 (0)	0.1–0.1	2.964 ± 3	6 (0)	0.98–8.99
04. Late Wetland	1.335 ± 1.9	6 (2)	0–4.64	0.094 ± NA	1 (0)	0.09–0.09	2.808 ± 2.8	6 (0)	1.06–8.3
05. Walnut Creek Outflow	2.108 ± 1	6 (0)	1.28–4.09	0.012 ± NA	1 (0)	0.01–0.01	2.996 ± 1.2	6 (0)	1.97–4.8

Additional Plots

Figure 15.4. Daily discharge (gallons per day or GPD) for the Outflow (i.e., sampling location 5) at the Walnut Creek Treatment Wetland Restoration Project calculated using continuous water level measurements and a flat weir equation. Note that daily discharge is represented in millions (M) of gallons per day.

Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration (WEIP)

Project Overview

Williams County

Project Size: 75 acres

Partner: Black Swamp Conservancy

ODNR Description: “This project will restore the floodplain along 75–acres near the Tiffin River. Restored wetlands and vegetation will filter nutrients and restore fish habitat. The project will also allow for re-introduction of threatened and endangered fish species.”¹⁶

Management Considerations

In addition to retaining nutrients, another goal of this Project was to allow for reintroduction of threatened and endangered fish species. However, due to seasonal loss of standing water, it appears that it will not be possible for fish to survive in any of the wetland areas at this Project. The floodplain reconnection is allowing Tiffin River floodwater to enter the Project but due to relatively dry weather conditions during the past two years, flooding of that area was rarely observed. The vernal pools only have standing water during a relatively brief period of the year due to the relatively low level of rainfall during the past two years but are performing as intended by retaining water, which reduces surface water runoff.

Sampling Approach

Construction at this Project was completed in 2022. Pre-construction monitoring was conducted in December 2021 and routine monitoring began in May 2022. This Project is relatively small with five small vernal pools (< 0.2 acres in area each) and a larger floodplain wetland area (~4 acres). The vernal pools seasonally flood (Figure 16.1) and the floodplain wetland has intermittent connection to the Tiffin River. All sampling locations (Figure 16.2) are sampled about once per season for water and once per year for soil. Researchers sample the Tiffin River and a nearby wetland that was pre-existing on the property, to compare the river and pre-existing wetland to the newly formed wetland pools.

¹⁶ “The Weisgerber-Pohlmann Nature Preserve.” h2.ohio.gov. Ohio Departments of Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environmental Protection, March 4, 2024. <https://h2.ohio.gov/project/tiffin-river-pohlmann-floodplain-restoration/>

Figure 16.1. One of the vernal pools at the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project on July 7, 2023, already dry just a few months after springtime flooding.

Sampling Locations

- 01. Vernal Pool 1
- 02. Vernal Pool 2
- 03. Vernal Pool 3
- 04. Vernal Pool 4
- 05. Vernal Pool 5
- 06. Flood plain wetland
- 07. Existing wetland
- 08. Tiffin River
- 09. Seepage spring

Figure 16.2. Aerial image of approximate location of sampling for water and soil samples and discrete manual measurements of water depth and physicochemical measurements at Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration project. The legend provides a brief description of each sampling point.

Sampling Location Water Depths

The five vernal pools and the floodplain wetland at this Project tended to be shallow or dry for most of the year (0–5 cm on average; Figure 16.3, Table B16.2). A seepage spring was discovered several months after construction was complete. The seepage spring outlet tended to be deeper than any of the vernal pools and held water for a greater portion of the year (Figure 16.3), likely due to greater groundwater influence. The vernal wetland pools at this Project experienced seasonal inundation, filling with water over winter and spring and drying through the summer and fall (Table B16.3). Water depth measurements were generally taken at sampling locations within pools, not always at the deepest point within pools.

Figure 16.3. Boxplots displaying variability in discrete, manually measured surface water depths (in centimeters) across sampling locations at the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project. Depths were measured approximately monthly from 2021–2023. For each boxplot, the thick line represents the median (middle) surface water depth across all

measurements. The boxes indicate the value range for 50% of the measured depths and the whiskers show the spread of depth values that are outside the 50% of the data points. Each overlying point represents individual water depth measurements and colors denote the season in which the measurement was taken, as indicated in the legend.

Surface Water Nutrient Concentrations

Dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) was below the detection limit in all vernal pool sampling locations (< 0.01 mg P/L). Total phosphorus (TP) was similar and very low in vernal pools (mean = 0.04 mg P/L; Table B16.4). Average DRP and TP were highest in the Tiffin River (0.07 and 0.1 mg P/L, respectively) and in the Existing Wetland (0.07 and 0.3 mg P/L respectively; Figure 16.4), which is likely to receive most of its water during river flooding events (Table B16.4). The observed P concentrations were low relative to other northwest Ohio rivers.

Total ammonia (NH_3) concentrations were very low or below detection limit (max = 0.076 mg N/L; Table 16.1). Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x) was low in the vernal pools (< 0.5 mg N/L) but higher in the floodplain wetland (1.6 mg N/L), existing wetland (2.6 mg N/L), Tiffin River (2.6 mg N/L), and seepage spring (3.5 mg N/L; Table 16.1). The same pattern was observed for total nitrogen (TN), with low concentrations present in the vernal pools (< 2 mg N/L) compared to the floodplain wetland (3.5 mg N/L), existing wetland (3.6 mg N/L), Tiffin River (3.1 mg N/L), and seepage spring (3.9 mg N/L) sampling locations (Table 16.1). The high concentration of NO_x and TN in the seepage spring would be consistent with it coming from agricultural runoff but the low variability in concentrations after rainfall is consistent with the source being groundwater. The outflow of the seepage spring is at a relatively high elevation on the downslope (~ 1 meter higher than the floodplain pool), suggesting that it has a shallow groundwater source.

Soil Nutrient Status

The highest soil conductivity was measured in sediments from the Tiffin River (940 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, Table B16.8). Soil conductivity was variable among vernal pools, ranging from 12 – 1278 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (Table B16.8), possibly because of differential evaporative concentration and different water sources feeding each pool. Soil pH was in the typical range of 6 – 7.7 and fairly consistent across all sampling locations, but the wetland soils (i.e., floodplain wetland and existing wetland) were on average slightly more acidic (6.3 – 6.6 ; Table B16.8).

Mehlich 3-extracted phosphorus (M3-P) was very low in vernal pools 1–4 (< 4 mg P/kg) but substantially higher in Vernal Pool 5 (18 mg P/kg). Average M3-P was highest at the floodplain wetland (24 mg P/kg), which is expected because this pool occasionally receives phosphorus (P) inputs from agricultural runoff carried by the Tiffin River that are generally higher in P concentration (Table B16.10). Average Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) levels were consistently moderate across the Project (51 – 104 mg P/kg; Figure 16.5), which indicates the soil is likely to sorb P and at low risk of P release (Table B16.10).

Water-extractable phosphate ($\text{H}_2\text{O-PO}_4$) was on average lower in the vernal pools (0–0.5 mg P/kg) and higher in the existing and floodplain wetlands and in the Tiffing River (0.6–1.1 mg P/kg). Average water-extractable nitrate ($\text{H}_2\text{O-NO}_3$) was similar across all sampling locations (2.6–5.9 mg N/kg), and water-extractable ammonia ($\text{H}_2\text{O-NH}_3$) was on average notably higher in the existing wetland (4.6 mg N/kg) than the newer vernal pools (0.2–1.3 mg N/kg; Table B16.12). Soil TP and TN concentrations were consistently moderate in all sampling locations, with TP ranging between 360–500 mg P/kg and TN from 630–1200 mg N/L (Table B16.12).

Monitoring Considerations & Future Efforts

In the coming year, we plan to install two water level loggers at this Project. These will support continuous collection of water level data and inform estimates of total input and output water volumes. Monitoring of this site will continue as planned with water samples collected seasonally and soil samples collected annually during the summer.

Non-Focal Projects: Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration (WEIP)

Figure 16.4. Time series of dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP, top panel) and total phosphorus (TP, bottom panel) concentrations in surface water samples collected at the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project from 2021–2023. Each symbol represents one sample point, colors denote the sampling locations, and shapes indicate the general category of the sampling locations, as indicated in the legend. Values below detection limit were replaced with zero. Connected circles represent samples collected within 30 days of each other.

Non-Focal Projects: Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration (WEIP)

Table 16.1. Summarized surface water nitrogen concentrations for the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project. Values are reported as mean ± standard deviation along with the number of summarized observations, the number of samples below detection limit (BDL), and range (min–max). Values below detection limit were replaced with zero for the calculation of summary statistics. Nitrate+Nitrite (NO_x), total ammonia (NH₃) and total nitrogen (TN) are reported. NA = data not collected or not enough data available. Note that some sampling locations may only have one observation available.

Sampling Location	Nitrate+Nitrite (mg N/L)			Total Ammonia (mg N/L)			Total Nitrogen (mg N/L)		
	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max	Mean ± SD	Sample Size (BDL)	Min–Max
01. Vernal Pool 1	0 ± 0	2 (2)	0–0	0 ± 0	2 (2)	0–0	0 ± 0	2 (2)	0–0
02. Vernal Pool 2	0.103 ± 0	2 (0)	0.08–0.12	0.008 ± 0	2 (1)	0–0.02	1.381 ± 1.4	2 (0)	0.42–2.34
03. Vernal Pool 3	0.108 ± 0	2 (0)	0.08–0.13	0 ± 0	2 (2)	0–0	1.737 ± 1.8	2 (0)	0.45–3.02
04. Vernal Pool 4	0.481 ± 0.6	2 (0)	0.07–0.89	0 ± 0	2 (2)	0–0	0.715 ± 0.6	2 (0)	0.31–1.12
05. Vernal Pool 5	0.104 ± NA	1 (0)	0.1–0.1	0 ± NA	1 (1)	0–0	1.956 ± NA	1 (0)	1.96–1.96
06. Floodplain wetland	1.57 ± 2.6	3 (1)	0–4.58	0.013 ± 0	3 (2)	0–0.04	3.53 ± 1.9	3 (0)	1.31–4.8
07. Existing wetland	2.592 ± NA	1 (0)	2.59–2.59	0 ± NA	1 (1)	0–0	3.575 ± NA	1 (0)	3.58–3.58
08. Tiffin River	2.578 ± 3.7	10 (0)	0.05–12.18	0.013 ± 0	10 (7)	0–0.08	3.117 ± 4.3	10 (0)	0.35–14.29
09. Seepage spring	3.506 ± 0.2	2 (0)	3.35–3.67	0 ± 0	2 (2)	0–0	3.885 ± 0.3	2 (0)	3.67–4.1

Figure 16.5. Soil Phosphate Sorption Capacity (SPSC) throughout the Weisgerber-Pohlman Nature Preserve - Restoration Project. Each circle denotes an approximate sampling location and is annotated with the mean SPSC for spatially clustered soil samples (0–5 cm). The number of samples in each cluster is shown in white font below the circles. The color of the circle indicates the range of SPSC values, as indicated in the legend. Negative SPSC values indicate potential for soils to release phosphate, while positive values indicate soils have capacity to sorb phosphate, based on Mehlich 3 extractions of P, Fe, and Al.

Appendix

Project List

Appendix Table 17.1. H2Ohio Initiative Projects routinely monitored in 2023. Geographic Base Crew, Four-letter Project Code, Project Name, and Monitoring Phase in 2022 and 2023. Intensively monitored focal projects are indicated in bold. Char = characterization; (Pre) = pre-construction; (Post) = post-construction, Y1 = 1st Year, Y2 = 2nd Year. BG = Bowling Green State University, HU = Heidelberg University, KS = Kent State University, UT = University of Toledo, WS = Wright State University.

Geographic Base Crew	Project Code	Project Name	2022 Monitoring Phase			2023 Monitoring Phase	
			Char. (Pre)	Char. (Post)	Routine Y1	Routine Y1	Routine Y2
Northwest Inland (BG)	FORB	Forder Bridge			•		•
	OAKE	Oakwoods East			•		•
	OAKW	Oakwoods West			•		•
	OOPR	Oak Openings Preserve			•		•
	OTSS	Otsego Schools	•			•	
	SJCO	St. Joseph Confluence			•		•
	SJRE	St. Joseph's Restoration			•		•
	VANO	Van Order			•		•
	WEIP	Weisgerber-Pohlman			•		•
Northwest Central (HU)	FRUW	Fruth Wetland			•		•
	REDB	Redhorse Bend			•		•
	SPRM	Springville Marsh		•		•	
	SRHE	Sandusky River Headwaters			•		•
	SUGB	Sugarcamp 7		•		•	
Northeast (KS)	TRUC	Trumbull Creek		•		•	
Northwest Coastal (UT)	DARR	Darby Refuge			•		•
	MAGM	Magee Marsh			•		•
	NORR	North Ridge			•		•
	OTTN	Ottawa National Wildlife Refuge			•		•
Southwest and Central (WS)	BROP	Brooks Park			•		•
	BWLK	Burntwood-Langenkamp			•		•
	MERW	Mercer Wetland	•			•	
	SPRC	Springcreek Confluence			•		•
	TIPC	Tipp City		•		•	
	WALC	Walnut Creek	•			•	

Additional Data

Soil and Water Chemistry Project Level Results

For each Non-focal Project, supplemental tables and figures are presented in an accompanying *Water and Soil Chemistry at Non-focal Projects Appendix (Appendix B)*, including the Sampling Locations, Sampling Location Water Depths, Surface Water Chemistry, and Soil Characteristics. Some elements within this document may be repeated in the Appendix.